

Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development

D1.3 – Report on project and SAB Meetings – Update 1

WP1 – Manage & Coordinate

30/05/2025

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Grant Agreement Number	101081179	Acronym	DIAMOND
Full Title	Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development		
Topic	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D1-02		
Funding scheme	HORIZON EUROPE, RIA – Research and Innovation Action		
Start Date	December 2022	Duration	48 Months
Project URL	http://www.climate-diamond.eu/		
EU Project Advisor	Silvia Vaghi		
Project Coordinator	Institute of Communications and Computer Systems - ICCS		
Deliverable	D1.3 – Report on project and SAB Meetings Update 1		
Work Package	WP1 – Manage & Coordinate		
Date of Delivery	Contractual	31/05/2025	Actual 30/05/2025
Nature	Report	Dissemination	Public
Lead Beneficiary	Institute of Communications and Computer Systems - ICCS		
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Keywords	project meetings; communication; project management; SAB meetings		

EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable's purpose is to act as an internal tool to review DIAMOND's progress and as a reference point for DIAMOND partners on their deliverables' and tasks' fulfilment regarding the agreed conditions by the partners and as proposed in the project's Grant Agreement.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

As described in the project's Quality Management Plan, online and physical (hybrid) meetings take place regularly in order for the consortium to discuss and collaborate during the project's time horizon. Hence, Executive Board Meetings (EBMs) are organised on a monthly basis and General Assembly (GA) meetings twice per year. The EBMs are hosted virtually, via Microsoft Teams, in one-hour sessions, while GA meetings take place either online in a two-day setup or physically (in a hybrid format, supported by Microsoft Teams, for online participation) back-to-back with other project events, such as workshops. Physical GA meetings without any accompanying events are generally avoided due to sustainability concerns. EBMs are organised in order to inform all DIAMOND partners on the progress of all Tasks and to guarantee that all milestones and deliverables are prepared in time. In this context, the ICCS administration team organises these monthly meetings and prepares a draft agenda, before finalising it with the rest of the partners.

During the second year of the project and the first half of its third year, one physical meeting was held, which took place in Lausanne, Switzerland on the 23rd and 24th of May 2024. In addition, during this 18-month period, 2 GA meetings and 8 EBMs were held online via Microsoft Teams. Both physical and online meetings are characterised by high attendance since almost all consortium partners are represented in each individual meeting, showcasing the partners' dedication to the project's progress and objectives.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This deliverable proves the successful organisation of the project's meetings as presented in its Grant Agreement, as well as the high level of participation from the consortium. Moreover, this report details the discussions held in these meetings, which showcase the progress and completion of the project's objectives as well as matters that are relevant to the scientific depth of the project's deliverables and milestone reports.

Preface

DIAMOND will update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity. It will further enhance modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies. This will be done via integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science. The project will develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establish vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

ICCS	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	EL	
BC3	ASOCIACION BC3 BASQUE CENTRE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE - KLIMA ALDAKETA IKERGAI	ES	
CESAR	KRATENA KURT	AT	
CICERO	CICERO SENTER FOR KLIMAFORSKNING	NO	
CYI	THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE	CY	
E4SMA	ENERGY ENGINEERING ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT SYSTEMS MODELING AND ANALYSIS SRL	IT	
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC IKE	EL	
COMILLAS	UNIVERSIDAD PONTIFICIA COMILLAS	ES	
ISINNOVA	ISTITUTO DI STUDI PER L'INTEGRAZIONE DEI SISTEMI (I.S.I.S) - SOCIETA' COOPERATIVA	IT	
SEURECO	SEURECO SOCIETE EUROPEENNE D'ECONOMIE SARL	FR	
UM	UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT	NL	
ESMIA	ESMIA CONSULTANTS INC.	CA	
USMF	THE UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND FOUNDATION INC	US	
UMD	UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND	US	
EPFL	ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE	CH	
ETH	EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH	CH	
UNIBAS	UNIVERSITAT BASEL	CH	
Imperial	IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE	UK	
Oxford	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	UK	
UCL	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	UK	

Executive Summary

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Use of AI disclaimer

During all meetings (including EBMs, GAs and SAB sessions), extensive draft notes have been manually kept by human participants. These minutes have undergone anonymisation and removal of any information that might be considered privileged and/or sensitive and parsed through AI (ChatGPT v4) to deliver summarised versions of the notes and synthesise them in concise minutes. The final output has been checked and approved for accuracy, and further edited (e.g., manual insertion of previously removed information when needed) by the contributing authors.

1 Introduction

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, regular and ad hoc meetings are organised during the project’s lifespan. Regular meetings (General Assembly Meetings) are organised twice a year in order to oversee the progress of all actions realised as well as to aid partners in fully comprehending the scientific work conducted in DIAMOND’s context. The Project Coordinator (ICCS) is in charge of formulating the meetings’ agenda, organising the meetings (cooperating with other partners) as well as informing all involved parties about the meetings’ time and location. In addition, online meetings (via Microsoft Teams) are organised regularly which allow partners to discuss specific issues regarding project deliverables, milestones and tasks. In this respect, ICCS also hosts monthly online meetings (Executive Board Meetings) in order that partners are in line with DIAMOND’s actions and progress. The Project Coordinator records all meetings and sessions, in the context of various work packages and activities as well as the project’s coordination and management. In this respect, this deliverable is related to the latter (i.e., General Assembly and Executive Board Meetings) for which the project’s administration team records meeting minutes and then shares them with the project’s partners on the internal data management system (MS2) ensuring that the whole consortium is informed about the project’s timelines, agreed plans and overall progress.

The table below depicts the meetings that were organised during M13-M30 of the project’s implementation (meetings during the period M1-M12 are reported in D1.2). EBMs take place monthly unless a GA meeting is planned for the same period. Moreover, some EBMs were not organised either due to their proximity to GA meetings, their proximity to the internal review meeting and the preparatory consortium-wide preparation meetings (September 2024), or due to low availability as a result of Easter and summer vacations.

Table 1. DIAMOND Project Meetings (covering period December 2023-May 2025)

Type of meeting		Date
Online	2 nd General Assembly Meeting	8 th and 9 th of January 2024
Online	Executive Board Meeting	28 th of February 2024
Online	Executive Board Meeting	27 th of March 2024
Online	Executive Board Meeting	24 th of April 2024
Physical	3 rd General Assembly Meeting	23 rd and 24 th of May 2024
Online	Executive Board Meeting	19 th of June 2024
Online	Executive Board Meeting	16 th of October 2024
Online	Executive Board Meeting	4 th of December 2024
Online	4 th General Assembly Meeting	29 th of January 2025
Online	Executive Board Meeting	26 th of March 2025
Online	Executive Board Meeting	30 th of April 2025

1.1 Purpose and scope

This deliverable aims to showcase a periodic report of all project meetings (physical and online), including the meetings’ agenda, list of attendees and meetings. Moreover, this deliverable includes any feedback provided by the Scientific Advisory Board from any online and physical communication, especially during dedicated SAB sessions, usually held within General Assembly Meetings.

1.2 Structure of the Document

Section 2 is dedicated to presenting the agenda and minutes of physical meetings, Section 3 showcases all details from online meetings, and Section 4 presents the SAB’s feedback.

2 Physical Meetings

2.1 General Assembly Meeting, 23-24 May 2024

The 3rd General Assembly Meeting of the project took place on the 23rd and 24th of May 2024 in Lausanne, Switzerland, on the EPFL campus, hosted by the project's EPFL partners. Some of the objectives of this two-day meeting were to discuss the progress of the 6 core models of the project, to host a couple of workshops to further understand the connection between the 6 core models of the project and other developments (e.g. soft-linking with other models and stakeholder engagement activities), to discuss the timeline of the following 12 months and to inform all partners on the work done by other collaborators. In this meeting, all project partners were represented either physically or online. Moreover, some of the project's SAB members participated in the relevant session.

2.1.1 Agenda

Day I: An update to all WPs & exchange with the SAB

Virtual participants: Zoom ([Link](#)) – Meeting ID: 629 6675 7780

Thursday, May 23, 2024, EPFL - Campus Ecublens, SG-0211 (all times in CEST/local)			
09:00 – 09:05	I.1	Welcome by Prof. Philippe Thalmann	EPFL
09:05 – 09:30	I.2	WP1 – Manage & Coordinate <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination & Management • Progress so far • Quality control (including review, review times) • Interim Report 	ICCS
09:30 – 10:30	I.3	WP2 – Codesign <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moving to Phase 2 of stakeholder engagement • Outcomes from the coordination of modelling/module teams stakeholder engagement requirements • Updated Multi-layered Stakeholder Engagement Strategy, requirements workshop & scenario workshops 	ISINNOVA & ETH
10:30 – 11:30	I.4	WP3 – Update & Upgrade <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model development progress • Brief presentation of current version of the models • Heading to the next update of the Model Development Strategy 	E4SMA & BC3
11:30 – 12:30	Lunch Break		
12:30 – 13:00	I.5	WP6 – Open <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progress on supporting tools • I²AM PARIS Platform progress • Synergies with other projects & communities • Strategy/Webinars on WP2-prescribed actions 	ICCS & HOLISTIC
13:00 – 13:45	I.6	WP4 – Integrate & Expand <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progress on module development • Presentation of Tasks beginning on M19 	Imperial
13:45 – 14:30	I.7	WP5 – Apply & Explore <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Summary of WP5 kick-off meeting • From model development to model use 	CICERO

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Project on scenario definition space and pipeline uncertainties •Scoping of activities for each task 	
14:30– 14:45	<i>Coffee Break</i>		
14:45 – 15:00	1.8	WP7 – Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Ideas for boosting our visual identity •Progress with regard to the CDE plan & KPIs •Ideas for website changes 	HOLISTIC
15:00 – 16:00	1.9	Scientific Advisory Board Welcome remarks, project progress/planning, feedback	SAB members, ICCS, all partners

Day II: Preparing the second stage of DIAMOND

Virtual participants: Zoom ([Link](#)) – Meeting ID: 656 9400 1334

Friday, May 24, 2024, EPFL - Campus Ecublens, SG-0211, (all times in CEST/local)			
09:00 – 09:15	II.1	Welcome notes and aims of Day-II	EPFL, ICCS
09:15 – 10:15	II.2	Organising work for RP2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timeline • Stage 2 deliverables • Task linkages and feedback flows 	ICCS
10:15 – 11:30	II.3	Cross-cutting themes on stakeholder engagement expectations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synthesis of research questions and engagement ideas from WPs 3 and 5 • Process of communication and feedback with WP4 	ETH, ISINNOVA, all partners
11:30 – 12:30	<i>Lunch break</i>		
12:30 – 14:00	II.4	Model development: Run-in for beta versions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation and demonstration of the first version of the aggregated CLEWs-EU model • Beta version of GEMINI-E3 EU • Reflections on how to exploit the models for stakeholder engagement • Aspirations for stakeholder engagement influencing model development across all IAMs 	Cyl, Imperial, ICCS, EPFL, E4SMA, BC3
14:00 – 14:15	<i>Coffee break</i>		
14:15 – 15:30	II.5	Module development: Towards integration <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circularity performance • Land use and nature-based solutions • Household heterogeneity • Climate impacts • Finance, labour, well-being • Behavioural aspects • Electricity system • Brief reflections on bilateral talks between partners on model-module integrations and further prospects for communication to foster integration 	Imperial, with feedback from all partners
15:30 – 15:45	II.6	Roundtable on partners' requirements <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchanging on partners' requirements on data and assumptions • Open discussion 	ICCS, All partners
15:45 – 16:00	II.7	Wrap-up	ICCS, EPFL

2.1.2 Minutes

Present on Meeting	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
4	Giannis Tolios	ICCS
5	Anastasis Giannousakis	ICCS
6	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3

7	Claudia Rodes	BC3
8	Russell Horowitz	BC3
9	Kurt Kratena	CESAR
10	Shivika Mittal	CICERO
11	Glen Peter	CICERO
12	Jan Ivar Korskbakken	CICERO
13	Ben Sanderson	CICERO
14	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
15	Sonja Sechi	E4SMA
16	Tomasso Pillon	E4SMA
17	Alessia Elia	E4SMA
18	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
19	Maria del Socorro Gómez	COMILLAS
20	Sara Lumbreras	COMILLAS
21	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
22	Carlo Sessa	ISINNOVA
22	Paul Zagamé	SEURECO
23	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
24	Hayat Mekki	SEURECO
25	Mark Sanders	UM
26	Sascha Serebriakova	UM
27	Prescott Morley	UM
28	Tania Treibich	UM
29	Eoghan O'Connell	UM
30	Marie Pied	ESMIA
31	Marc Vielle	EPFL
32	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
33	Philippe Thalmann	EPFL
34	Stephanie Briers	ETH
35	Bianca Vienni-Baptista	ETH
36	Ulf Hahnel	UNIBAS
37	Rui Mata	UNIBAS
38	Lukas Engel	UNIBAS
39	Leigh Martindale	Imperial
40	Vignesh Sridharan	Imperial
41	Adam Hawkes	Imperial
42	Serguey Maximov	UCL
43	Isabella Butnar	UCL
44	Pietro Lubello	UCL
45	Cecilie Mauritzen	SAB
46	David McCollum	SAB
47	Lukas Hermwille	SAB

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
Day I			

Welcome	The meeting started with Prof Philippe Thalmann greeting all participants and providing a brief presentation about EPFL.		
WP1	<p>Next, Dr Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) took the floor to present the progress on WP1. On Task 1.1, he briefed the consortium on the requirements for the upcoming reporting period including information on the SyGMA platform, details on the financial report, which should be coordinated with ICCS administration, and summarised the elements of Part B regarding the project’s technical reporting, stating that a template will be shared with all partners. A deadline for the requested items (i.e., WP leaders to deliver on the descriptions for their packages) was set for the end of June so everything can be delivered by the end of July. Dr Nikas encouraged partners to include significant progress made during this RP that is not yet described in any deliverables (e.g., model development). In this context, Dr Konstantinos Koasidis (ICCS) proposed that the use of schematics can also be beneficial.</p> <p>Next, he proceeded to present the progress on Task 1.2 focusing on summarising the deliverables for months 14 to 18, briefing the partners on the timeline of the deliverables for the following 12 months and overviewing the project’s milestones until M26. Then, he briefly presented D1.2 and requested that all partners track bilateral meetings and inform the ICCS administration. Lastly, regarding Task 1.3, he informed the consortium on the 2nd SAB session highlights (feasibility issues, practitioner-based approach and synergies with sister projects).</p>	<p>Update involved scientists’ info on SyGMA</p> <p>Provide guidelines for financial reporting</p> <p>Share templates & examples</p> <p>Prepare financial statements and use of resources documentation</p> <p>Prepare WP progress reports</p>	<p>All partners</p> <p>ICCS</p> <p>ICCS</p> <p>ICCS</p> <p>WP leaders</p>
WP2	<p>The session focused on reviewing progress and planning next steps for the co-design process and stakeholder engagement activities. Dr. Stephanie Briers (ETH) confirmed that Stages 1 and 2 of Phase 1 have been completed and presented the full co-design timeline until October. Key deadlines include finalising the jointly framed problem statement in May and formulating the first set of stakeholder-informed research questions by August. The internal workshop that will take place on Day II of the meeting was discussed in terms of timing and expected output. Dr. Briers also presented a thematic mapping of research questions and teams, using the jointly framed problem statement as an example, which informed further discussion on stakeholder feedback for WPs 3 and 5.</p> <p>Mr. Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) then summarised progress on Deliverable 2.2 and Tasks 2.3.1 and 2.3.2, noting that 73 stakeholders were contacted, with 53 confirming willingness to engage. He provided an overview of stakeholder characteristics and presented initial details for the Requirements Workshop, including its rationale, scope, and format. A draft agenda is expected shortly. A discussion followed between Dr. Vienni-Baptista and Mr. Carlo Sessa (ISINNOVA) regarding reporting of the workshop. Mr. Sessa concluded by presenting options for structuring the Requirements Workshop discussions.</p> <p>Partners agreed that inputs from WP2 should be incorporated into Deliverable 3.2, with Dr. Shivika Mittal (CICERO) suggesting the inclusion of scenario definition issues.</p>	<p>Preparation for the Requirements Workshop</p>	<p>ISINNOVA</p>

<p>WP3</p>	<p>The WP3 progress meeting provided a detailed review of model development across the consortium, highlighting timelines, key deliverables, and coordination efforts. Dr. Baptiste Boitier (SEURECO) presented the development status of the NEMESIS World model, noting enhancements such as household disaggregation by income and consumption, and summarising bilateral meetings with EPFL and CESAR on hydrogen and household heterogeneity. He outlined ongoing data processing, coding, and parametrisation work, and confirmed that Deliverables D3.2 and D3.3 are in progress with submission expected per schedule. Dr. Sigit Perdana (EPFL) reported on GEMINI-E3, including advances in air pollutant and household modelling. He noted some timeline shifts—hydrogen modelling is now due by end-2024, and the nesting structure by September 2024. The model has already been showcased at three conferences. Discussions followed on hydrogen, ammonia, and air pollutant data (GTAP) with CICERO.</p> <p>Mr. Giannis Tolios and Dr. Anastasis Giannousakis (ICCS) reported OPEN-PROM’s progress, focusing on open-source adoption, spatial upgrades, and WP4 linkages, with further development needed for MS8. Dr. Dirk-Jan van de Ven (BC3) presented GCAM-Europe’s roadmap, including immediate priorities before and after WP4 integration, geographical coverage details, and use of FAO and Eurostat data. He flagged upcoming updates in crop trading granularity and discussed water usage data with Imperial. Dr. Constantinos Taliotis (CYI) updated on CLEWs-EU, stating the aggregated model is nearly ready for GitHub and that calibration will use 2018–2022 data. The disaggregated model draft is due by July 2025, and the final version by November 2025, with electricity and transport modules ready by end of 2024. He also proposed a bilateral internal review with Dr. Koasidis, who suggested broader participation. Dr. Mittal raised the challenge of reviewing unfamiliar models, recommending joint review of documentation, which was supported by E4SMA’s Dr. Sechi. Dr. Mittal also proposed a consortium-wide survey on data sources.</p> <p>Finally, Dr. Sechi (E4SMA) presented the OMNIA model’s update timeline via Gantt chart and detailed plans for Deliverable D3.2 (due November 2024), including soft linkages and sectoral designs. She noted current development status and next steps, while Dr. Sergey Maximov (UCL) highlighted industry modelling progress, particularly steel production via different technologies. A heat demand calculation example closed the session.</p>	<p>Prepare D3.2 and D3.3</p> <p>Finalise Hydrogen modelling and nesting structure design</p> <p>Enhancements to link GCAM-Europe with WP4 models</p> <p>Upload CLEWs-EU aggregated version in GitHub</p>	<p>SEURECO, E4SMA</p> <p>EPFL</p> <p>BC3</p> <p>ICCS, Imperial, CYI,</p>
<p>WP4</p>	<p>Following this, the discussion moved to WP4 for which the methodology and structure were presented, with a focus given on WP tasks and the responsible partners. It was also mentioned that the WP has just started. A brief summary of modelling interlinkages for WP3 and WP4 models was presented.</p> <p>Dr Maximov demonstrated the ENGAGE model, a materials model, which uses PIOLab to disaggregate the steel production sector. In this scope, he also introduced the consortium to the MAgPIE model, presenting a schematic illustration of its interlinkages with OMNIA.</p>		

	<p>Following this, Dr Ben Sanderson (CICERO) took the floor to present Task 4.4, introducing the METEOR model, which has a new improved version. In this context, he demonstrated some preliminary results from the model as well as the next steps for its use and development. Next, Ms Sasha Serebriakova (UM) provided the consortium with a general update on Task 4.5, presenting a figure on cooperation among models and finance, labour and consumption. Then, she presented the main takeaways from the literature, focusing on identified limitations. In this context, Mr Prescott Morley (UM) presented the main literature takeaways regarding the role of consumption in technology diffusion. Similarly, Mr Eoghan O'Connell (UM) presented the main literature insights on labour dynamics, focusing on issues such as the current status of labour in IAMs, skills and training for green jobs as well as challenges in worker transitions.</p> <p>Then, Mr Lukas Engel (UNIBAS) presented Task 4.6, highlighting the behavioural aspects taken into consideration (micro-level). In addition, he presented the interlinkages with Tasks 4.3 and 4.5 for socio-demographic variables. His presentation also included the effects of meso- and macro-level parameters (e.g., extreme weather events) on behavioural aspects. Lastly, regarding the current status of the work done, he presented some experimental data on electric vehicles.</p>		
WP5	<p>Next, Dr Peters took the floor presenting an overview of WP5 tasks, focusing on Task 5.1 which examines vetting and classification issues, bias on the scenario database, parametric and structural uncertainties in open SCM emulators as well as harmonisation and infilling processes. Following this, he described D5.1, presenting its ideal structure, and mentioning that it should be delivered by January 2025. Moreover, he demonstrated a figure on existing scenarios and which of them are assessed by IPCC. In this context, he presented the process for D5.1 and the definition of scenarios by IS92, ARES and AR6, mentioning the criteria for the IS92 are taken from IPCC. Lastly, he and Dr Nikas had a short discussion on the different scenario definitions.</p>	Prepare D5.1	CICERO
WP6	<p>Regarding WP6, Dr Koasidis took the floor presenting an overview of the deliverables and milestones prepared so far, mentioning that 7 deliverables are already available on the project's website. Then, he briefed the partners on the update of the Data Management Plan, stating that 11 publications and 5 datasets that acknowledge the project are also available in the project's Zenodo repository. Next, he presented communities of practice and webinars that can be organised in the context of DIAMOND. He suggested 5 topics, with Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) encouraging partners to propose more topics.</p> <p>Next, he summarised the synergies with the WorldTrans project, focusing on improving human behaviour modelling and user-centred applications as well as how WPs from these two projects can interact.</p> <p>Moreover, Dr Xexakis presented the collaboration with the MAIA</p>	<p>Suggest topics for DIAMOND webinars</p> <p>Publish a demo version of the new I2AM PARIS interface</p>	<p>All partners</p> <p>HOLISTIC</p>

	<p>project which works as an aggregator for Horizon research results. Then, he informed the consortium that a demonstration version of the new I²AM PARIS interface would be shortly available. He also presented a design methodology for developing open and policy-relevant platforms. Lastly, he presented the progress on the validation routines and the development pipelines.</p>		
WP7	<p>Afterwards, Dr Xexakis presented WP7, demonstrating the planning for each Task and the overview of the relevant deliverables. He presented Task 7.3, focusing on the project's targets and measured impacts. He mentioned that the project's website, social media accounts as well as Newsletters and Press Releases are demonstrating good progress so far, mostly achieving the set targets. He also stated that the project has published 11 research articles and 13 conference papers/presentations. He also mentioned that the consortium should expect a higher impact later on since the majority of project outcomes are still under development.</p> <p>Regarding the project's CDE plan, he mentioned that there are no significant changes, focusing on the project's synergies with other EU projects and communities of practice, such as the MAIA network. On Task 7.1, he stated that there are no major updates apart from new content being constantly uploaded to the project's website.</p> <p>Next, Dr Xexakis, Dr Vienni-Baptista, Dr Mittal and Dr Koasidis had a discussion on WP2 publications and in general the target of the project's scientific publications, encouraging each partner to pursue publishable material.</p>		
SAB Session	<p>The SAB session started with Dr Nikas presenting to the SAB members the progress of the project so far. He presented an SDG modelling study done acknowledging the project, a list of best practices for participatory modelling, the studies that were showcased at the EGU conference, some preparatory work done for stakeholder engagement activities, the development of the CLEWs-EU model, a set of transparency procedures, surveys done with other projects, interactions with other communities and the updates of the I²AM PARIS platform, as well as a cooperation with the municipality of Athens.</p> <p>Next, the SAB members took the floor, with a member of the SAB commencing a discussion about the reporting process for Horizon Europe projects, and stressed the importance of consortium partners being aware of the project's KPIs and their progress.</p> <p>Another member, asked if the consortium is considering participating in COP-29, with Dr Nikas replying that the project's models are still in development, hence they cannot provide many policy insights yet and that it would be better to consider participating in upcoming COPs. Next, the member also suggested additional initiatives such as the UN High-Level Political Framework on Sustainable Development and the IPCC surveys. Dr Nikas and Dr Mittal replied that these recommendations are very useful and that the consortium is already running some relevant surveys.</p> <p>Then, another member asked if the consortium has considered how to adapt to potential changes in the policy landscape based on</p>		

	<p>contemporary developments. He also stressed the importance of models being able to examine extreme events. In the first matter, Dr Nikas replied that the SAB's feedback on this can be very useful and on the latter that project partners are already examining the models' robustness.</p> <p>In addition, an SAB member and Dr Vienni-Baptista had a discussion on the effectiveness of the project's participatory framework and Dr Nikas had a short discussion on citizen participation with members of the SAB, focusing on practitioners.</p> <p>Lastly, Dr Nikas thanked all SAB members for their attendance and insightful comments.</p>		
<p>Day II</p>			
<p>Welcome notes and aims of Day II</p>	<p>Dr Nikas greeted the consortium and presented the agenda for the meeting's 2nd Day.</p>		
<p>Organising work for RP2</p>	<p>Dr. Koasidis highlighted that the second reporting period will be significantly more intensive than the first, with most deliverables and activity concentrated before Month 36. All tasks are expected to be active soon, and close coordination will be essential due to strong interdependencies across work packages (WPs). He emphasised understanding these dependencies, especially between WPs 2 and 3, where technical questions from partners drive collaboration. Key upcoming milestones include MS6 (Nov 2024, M24) on stakeholder engagement and D3.2 (model strategy update), which will require early input from MS6.</p> <p>For WP2–WP5 coordination, D5.1 (M26) will rely on feedback from WP2-organised stakeholder workshops. ETH will lead meetings to support this. Additionally, WP2's first deliverable (M30) must align with D5.1 timelines. The full interaction between WPs 2, 3, and 5 will culminate in D3.3 (final model strategy), integrating feedback, particularly for WP4 links.</p> <p>For WP3–WP4 interlinkages, MS8 will require initial working versions of all IAMs and inform second-period reporting. Final versions of CLEWs-EU and NEMESIS-World (D3.4 & D3.5) and all D4.1–D4.4 deliverables are due by M36, demanding strong coordination. Additionally, MS7 on ENGAGE and MAgPIE models must be ready by M26. Lastly, he pointed to the transition into Reporting Period 3, underscoring D2.6 on stakeholder feedback and WP6's role in ensuring procedural openness.</p>		
<p>Cross-cutting themes on stakeholder engagement expectations</p>	<p>The next session started with Dr Briers explaining to the meeting's participants how the following workshop would function. She said that a set of questions will be presented that participants will have to answer, being grouped into 5 different teams on different thematics. She also mentioned that an online board in <i>Miro</i> will be available for online participants to join in break-out rooms..</p> <p>Next, Dr Briers continued by guiding all online and in-person participants through the process. The internal workshop then took place (see more details in D2.4 and D2.5).</p> <p>After the ETH workshop, ISINNOVA presented the regenerative</p>		

	<p>approach, explaining its foundation in the 3 Horizons methodology and the Transition Scenarios Meta-Model, which includes mid-term and long-term scenario pathways. Mr Sessa clarified that this approach will be more prominent in the upcoming Foresight Workshops, while the Requirements Workshop will focus on research questions gathered so far. He outlined the structure of the workshop, which will include 4–5 break-out sessions (Upstream, Industry, Downstream, End-use) with two rounds to allow broader stakeholder engagement.</p> <p>Discussions followed on workshop preparation, including the importance of communicating material clearly and concisely. ISINNOVA noted that stakeholders will be introduced to the regenerative approach through multiple channels (invitations, briefs, references, and workshop presentations). The team confirmed plans to inform partners about stakeholder selection and will send a survey to 53 identified stakeholders. The stakeholder database remains open for consortium contributions. The target is to engage around 20 stakeholders in the requirements workshop, and WP leaders will be invited once internal alignment on the workshop is achieved.</p> <p>There was brief coordination on the timeline of the organisation of the requirements workshop, stating that it might be useful to schedule it for September.</p>		
<p>Model development: Run-in for beta versions</p>	<p>The two models (CLEWs-EU) and GEMINI-E3-EU that are at a more advanced stage were presented and discussed.</p> <p>CLEWs-EU (Dr. Taliotis & Dr. Sridharan)</p> <p>Dr. Taliotis introduced the CLEWs-EU model, explaining the CLEWs framework and showing the model’s modular structure and interlinkages. He detailed the energy module, covering primary energy, electricity & heat generation, and three end-use sectors (buildings, transport, industry). The model’s time granularity and horizon were described, noting that energy demand and mileage inputs are exogenous. For industry, the team is considering outputting some results in physical units rather than generic terms. Data sources focus heavily on Eurostat, and documentation and progress tracking via Excel are underway. Initial model runs were shared to illustrate typical outputs.</p> <p>Dr. Sridharan presented the land & water module, explaining its foundation on OSeMOSYS and water balance mechanisms. He described the land system—land cover types, technology thresholds, and EU land cover data—and the representation of ten major crops with yield data from GAEZ and FAO. Water demand is modeled endogenously for agriculture and power sectors, exogenously for public supply and industry; desalination and energy module links were also detailed. Challenges and ongoing tasks include data collection and country-specific issue identification. Indicative results were shown.</p> <p>Discussions:</p> <p>Dr. Mittal proposed a WP3 workshop to unify data sources across models.</p> <p>On glacier-/snow-covered lands as “usable” in extreme scenarios, Dr.</p>	<p>Organise a workshop for WP3 modelling teams on data sources</p>	<p>CICERO, all WP3 modelling teams</p>

	<p>Sridharan noted modeling difficulties.</p> <p>The shipping sector’s inclusion was suggested; Dr. Taliotis said it was omitted initially due to limited sectoral interactions but could be added.</p> <p>Differences between CLEWs-EU and GCAM data approaches were highlighted by Dr. van de Ven and Dr. Mittal, who suggested a follow-up discussion.</p> <p>Biomass production was discussed; CLEWs-EU currently excludes crop waste but can model biomass use tied to land types, important for BECCS scenarios.</p> <p>Livestock feed issues and the absence of separate feed crop categories were acknowledged as areas for further exploration, especially for country-specific modeling.</p> <p>Dr. Sridharan suggested compiling data lists and soliciting feedback for improvement.</p> <p>GEMINI-E3 EU (Dr. Marc Vielle)</p> <p>Dr. Vielle presented how GEMINI-E3 constructs its Current Policies Scenario from 2017 to 2050, using population, GDP growth, and energy price assumptions. The model is calibrated on historical data (2017-2022) excluding COVID impacts, aiming to replicate the electricity mix closely and adjust GTAP data as needed. The scenario integrates the EU’s Fit for 55 package and the European Green Deal (including CBAM, new EU-ETS). Links between the Green Deal and the DIAMOND project were highlighted, with inquiries on task responsibility for these links.</p> <p>Discussions:</p> <p>Use of NECPs is limited to some EU countries; no dedicated task exists for the Green Deal but Task 3.1 (model development) is most relevant. Scenario development also involves WP5 teams.</p> <p>Harmonisation across models and projects was discussed, with Dr. Koasidis noting that different core model parameters may require harmonisation in specific exercises.</p> <p>Dr. Kratena suggested sensitivity analyses for accelerating EU decarbonization targets from 2050 to 2040. Dr. Vielle welcomed methods to incorporate EU-ETS mechanisms effectively.</p> <p>Dr. Mittal emphasised understanding each model’s needs to ensure harmonisation for WP5 progress.</p> <p>Vetting processes for scenarios were discussed with Dr. Boitier.</p> <p>Data sources for reference scenarios were debated: SSPs (with newer data) vs. the 2024 EU Ageing Report, discussed by Dr. van de Ven and Dr. Korsbakken.</p>		
<p>Module development: Towards integration</p>	<p>The last session began with Prof. Adam Hawkes summarizing the WP4 presentations from the first day. Dr. Maximov then presented on circular economy modeling, outlining the next six months’ steps, ongoing discussions with GCAM and OPEN-PROM teams for synergies, and explaining the linkages between OMNIA and ENGAGE. He also gave an overview of upcoming analyses related to iron and steel. Dr. Mittal highlighted the focus on land use modeling, the need to gather data from MAgPIE for OMNIA, and efforts to improve energy conversion within OMNIA.</p>		

	<p>Dr. Kratena shared progress on household heterogeneity, discussing the conceptual framework, data and methodology advances, and plans for integration with related tasks, including connections to WP5’s research questions. Dr. Mittal then presented climate modeling next steps, illustrating how climate impacts various inputs and discussing data challenges with Dr. Sridharan, particularly concerning crop yields. Discussions followed on labor productivity functions between Dr. Mittal and Dr. Boitier.</p> <p>Mr. Engel introduced work on behavioral aspects and climate action preferences, describing the UNIBAS experiment’s progress, data collection across EU countries, and secondary analyses on psychological drivers and extreme weather events. Ms. Serebriakova and Mr. Morley covered financial and household dynamics, respectively, including proposed models addressing liquidity constraints, links to behavioral studies, and agent-based modeling approaches, with cooperation offers to modeling teams. Mr. O’Connell detailed labor dynamics research focusing on skills, occupational mobility, and regional movement. The importance of labor issues for scenario modeling was emphasized, along with discussions on feasible implementation steps and potential use of policy inputs like WACCs.</p> <p>Dr. Lumbreras and Ms. Gómez Pérez presented the electricity modeling task and the OpenTEPES model, covering its scope, architecture, and integration with core models like TIAM-ECN. They shared example results and described ongoing model enhancements. Dr. Mittal encouraged focusing stakeholder questions on electricity modeling and recommended that the COMILLAS team consult existing WP3 questions to ensure coverage.</p>		
Wrap-up	<p>Dr Nikas and Dr Koasidis concluded the meeting by mentioning that the proposed open discussion had already taken place with so many insightful questions and discussions, and finally thanking EPFL partners for hosting the event and all online participants for attending.</p>		

3 Remote (Online) Meetings

3.1 General Assembly Meeting (8-9 January 2024)

The 2nd General Assembly Meeting of the project took place on the 8th and 9th of January 2024 online via Microsoft Teams. Some of the objectives of this two-day meeting were to discuss the project's progress over the last 6 months, the current developments on its core models and the next steps for the following 12-month period. All partners were represented as well as the SAB, for which a relevant session was held in order for its members to provide their feedback.

3.1.1 Agenda

Day I: An update to all WPs & exchange with the SAB

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Monday, January 8, 2024 (all times in CET)			
09:00 – 09:05	I.1	Welcome	ICCS
09:05 – 09:30	I.2	WP1 – Manage & Coordinate <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination & Management • Progress so far • Quality control (including review, review times) 	ICCS
09:30 – 10:30	I.3	WP2 – Codesign <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outcomes of mutual understanding workshops and brief plan on engagement activities • Progress on the Multi-layered Stakeholder • Engagement Strategy & Database and brief plan on engagement activities 	ISINNOVA & ETH
10:30 – 10:45	Coffee Break		
10:30 – 11:45	I.4	WP3 – Update & Upgrade <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated Model Development Strategy and planned synergies with WP4 • Model development progress • Current version of the models 	E4SMA & BC3
11:45 – 12:30	I.5	WP4 – Integrate & Expand <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Module meetings • Progress on module development 	Imperial
12:30 – 13:15	I.6	WP5 – Apply & Explore <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan for kicking off WP5 in Year 2 • From model development to model use • Introduction to scenario pipeline uncertainties 	CICERO
13:15 – 14:00	Lunch Break		
14:00 – 14:40	I.7	WP6 – Open <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vetting and visualisation tools • I²AM PARIS Platform progress • Synergies with other projects & communities 	ICCS & HOLISTIC

14:40 – 15:00	I.8	WP7 – Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ideas for boosting our visual identity• Progress with regard to the CDE plan & KPIs• Ideas for website changes	HOLISTIC
15:00 – 16:00	I.9	Scientific Advisory Board Welcome remarks, project progress/planning, feedback	SAB members, ICCS, all partners

Day II: Defining the role of stakeholders in the project

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Tuesday, January 9, 2024 (all times in CET)			
09:00 – 09:15	II.1	Synopsis of Day I and aims of Day II:	ICCS
09:15 – 10:15	II.2	What's next for stakeholder engagement? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planned workshops and activities in the three phases of co-design and co-development Discussion, reflections on codesign so far 	ETH & ISINNOVA
10:15 – 10:30	<i>Coffee break</i>		
10:30 – 12:30	II.3	Understanding stakeholder engagement expectations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-developing models with stakeholders: Revisiting the model development strategy in the context of engaging with external stakeholders and using their preferences Co-designing model expansions with stakeholders: Envisaging how we can integrate stakeholder feedback from engagement activities to planned module developments and linkages Co-creating scenarios with stakeholders: Eliciting priorities and co-creating research questions relevant to different societal priorities and stakeholder interests Open discussion 	All partners
12:30 – 13:30	<i>Lunch break</i>		
13:30 – 15:00	II.4	Designing our engagements <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aligning actions to WP tasks Deciding on engagement formats When will engagements happen WP contact point engagement planning 	ETH, ISINNOVA, E4SMA, BC3, Imperial, CICERO, All partners
15:00 – 15:15	II.5	Closing discussion and next steps Open discussion with a focus on timelines	ICCS, ETH, All partners
15:15 – 15:30	II.6	Wrap-up	ICCS

3.1.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Thomas Nikolakakis	ICCS
4	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
5	Natasha Frilingou	ICCS
6	Eleftheria Zisarou	ICCS

7	Anastasis Giannousakis	ICCS
8	Panagiotis Fragkos	ICCS
9	Dirk-Jan Van de Ven	BC3
10	Jon Sampedro	BC3
11	Claudia Rodes	BC3
12	Russell Horowitz	BC3
13	Kurt Kratena	CESAR
14	Shivika Mittal	CICERO
15	Glen Peters	CICERO
16	Ben Sanderson	CICERO
17	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
18	Norman Steinert	CICERO
19	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
20	Elpida Gkiouleka	CYI
21	Alessandro Chiodi	E4SMA
22	Tomasso Pilon	E4SMA
23	Sonja Sechi	E4SMA
24	Maurizio Gargiulo	E4SMA
25	Gabrielle Cassetti	E4SMA
26	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
27	Sara Lumbreras	COMILLAS
28	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
29	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
30	Paul Zagamé	SEURECO
31	Pierre Le Mouël	SEURECO
32	Eoghan O'Connell	UM
33	Mark Sanders	UM
34	Tania Treibich	UM
35	Prescott Morley	UM
36	Sascha Serebriakova	UM
37	Marie Pied	ESMIA
38	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
39	Marc Vielle	EPFL
40	Bianca Vienni-Baptista	ETH
41	Stephanie Briers	ETH
42	Lukas Engel	UNIBAS
43	Adam Hawkes	Imperial
44	Leigh Martindale	Imperial
45	Vignesh Sridharan	Imperial
46	Michael Obersteiner	Oxford
47	James Price	UCL
48	Isabela Butnar	UCL
49	Alvaro Calzadilla	UCL
50	Steve Pye	UCL
51	Serguey Maximov	UCL
52	Pietro Lubello	UCL
53	Jessica Jewel	SAB
54	Stephanie Waldhoff	SAB
55	Cecilie Mauritzen	SAB

56	Brian O’Gallachoir	SAB
57	Steve Smith	SAB
58	David McCollum	SAB
59	Hannah Daly	SAB
60	Lukas Hermwill	SAB

Minutes: Main issues discussed			
Day 1			
Item	Description		
Welcome	The General Assembly (GA) meeting started with Dr Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) greeting all participants and summarising the agenda of the 1 st day of the meeting.		
WP1	<p>Dr. Nikas presented WP1, starting with the overall project pipeline and WP interactions. He updated partners on SyGMA developments (Task 1.1) and informed them that ICCS would request researcher information from each partner. On Task 1.2 (scientific coordination), he confirmed Deliverables 1.1, 1.2, and 7.2 were delivered on time, D2.4 was shared with internal reviewers, and outlined the deliverables and milestones due in the next 12 months. He also mentioned D1.2, a periodic report covering GA and internal progress meetings.</p> <p>Regarding Task 1.3, the SAB synthesis remains unchanged, but highlights from SAB feedback were prepared, containing insights on stakeholder engagement and modelling. Dr. Nikas then discussed the project’s long-term outlook (Months 14–36), including future workshops. A discussion followed with Dr. Mittal on how SAB feedback relates to stakeholder engagement, with Dr. Nikas underlining the value of SAB input regardless of direct participation. Dr. Briers echoed the usefulness of SAB feedback and, along with Dr. Nikas, discussed synergies with sister projects. Dr. Koasidis reminded the group of SAB member Dr. Mauritzen’s proposal to link DIAMOND with WorldTrans.</p>	Request feedback on researchers’ information	ICCS
WP2	<p>Mr. Cassolà (ISINNOVA) presented the 2nd Phase of WP2 (M19–M36), including a flow diagram of the co-design process. He presented the initial stakeholder mapping, the categorisation, and requested contributions from partners that haven’t done so yet. He also discussed the stakeholder survey, pointing out some delays and questions around IAM familiarity.</p> <p>Upcoming engagement activities include updating D2.1, strategic foresight workshops, and citizen-driven foresight. A discussion followed with Dr. Mittal on including multiple themes in workshops and interaction with WP5. Prof. Pye raised targeting questions, and Mr. Cassolà emphasized the importance of balancing the stakeholder pool. Dr. Peters and</p>		

	<p>Dr. Nikas discussed the expert categorisation, and Dr. Xexakis proposed outreach strategies for database gaps.</p> <p>Dr. Mittal and Dr. Nikas raised issues about expert interview processes and the need to clearly define the contribution of each WP. Dr. Nikas stressed WP2 should lead stakeholder engagement. He and Mr. Cassolà also discussed WP2–WP3 coordination and the Requirements workshop timeline. Dr. Koasidis proposed clarifying all steps in the updated strategy.</p> <p>Dr. Briers (ETH) then presented progress on Phase 1, focusing on mutual understanding and summarising D2.2’s timeline and actions. She reviewed Phase 1 results by theme and outlined next steps for Stage 3 to be discussed on Day 2. Dr. Mittal mentioned a different approach to research questions in DIAMOND compared to other projects. Dr. Nikas noted ambiguity remains, and options will be explored further in Day 2 discussions.</p>		
WP3	<p>Ms. Sechi (E4SMA) opened with a coordination overview for WP3, focusing on key steps, WP2 alignment, and designing a common modelling strategy. She also presented the WP3 timeline, deliverables, and milestones. Each of the six models then presented updates. Dr. van de Ven (BC3) outlined the GCAM-Europe development through five update steps, highlighted EU and regional coverage, and discussed data sources and linkages with WP4, WP2, and WP5. Ms. Sechi also presented regional disaggregation work on OMNIA and sectoral updates, with further input expected from ESMIA, Imperial, and UCL. Ms. Pied (ESMIA) described upstream sector developments, including emissions for LNG, hydrogen, and biofuels. Prof. Pye illustrated steel industry processes and potential links with ENGAGE and other sectors. Dr. Taliotis (CYI) described CLEWs_EU’s progress, including two model versions (regional and disaggregated), development timelines, module interactions (energy, water, land), and coordination with WP4 tasks. Dr. Perdana (EPFL) presented GEMINI-E3 EU’s progress, including its structure (24 regions, 13 sectors), GTAP database foundation, two model versions, and interlinkages with WP4. The model is already featured in two publications and major conferences. Dr. Boitier (SEURECO) shared the NEMESIS World timeline and MRIO database synthesis, also touching on software enhancements (notably household grouping) and recent bilateral and workshop engagements. Dr. Giannousakis presented the OPEN-PROM model’s overview, action plan (13 items), and development timeline, also covering transparency and openness aspects.</p>		
WP4	<p>Regarding WP4, Dr Mittal commenced by presenting the list and a brief summary of the Tasks She provided an illustration of the WP’s timeline as well as the delivery dates for deliverables and milestones, mentioning that only Tasks 4.5</p>		

	<p>and 4.6 have already started. Then she provided a description of Task 4.1 and a figure showcasing its interlinkages (OMNIA and ENGAGE models). Similarly, she provided a schematic presentation of Task 4.2 (interlinking OMNIA and MAgPIE). Dr Ben Sanderson (CICERO) described Task 4.4 and provided a schematic demonstration of its interlinkages (IAMs + Climate and land allocation models). He also presented the framework used for climate impact and adaptation models, introducing the METEOR model with an illustration of its functions; a beta version is available on GitHub. He finished his presentation by briefing the consortium on the Task’s next steps. Then, Prof Tania Treibich (UM) described Task 4.5, mentioning its aim and procedures. She also summarised the progress made so far. Moreover, she mentioned that this task focuses on the fields of finance, labour and consumption and the work that needs to be done on each one focusing on literature review, modelling and integration. In this context, Dr Eoghan O’Connell (UM) and Dr Prescott Morley (UM) intervened to present the modelling aspects of labour and consumption patterns respectively. Lastly, Mr Lukas Engel (UNIBAS) took the floor, presenting the general idea (behavioural “module”) behind Task 4.6, demonstrating a schematic presentation of data inputs and IAM interactions. In this context, he briefed the consortium on the Task’s current status, mentioning, inter alia, meetings that have already been placed with WP3 modelling teams and the design of the study. Furthermore, he briefed the partners on the next steps in data collection and its assessment, stressing the need to discuss linkages and the possibility of the general population interacting with IAMs. In this context, Prof Mark Sanders (UM) and Mr Engel had a discussion on a bilateral communication for data collection.</p>		
<p>WP5</p>	<p>Dr Peters opened the session on WP5 by presenting an overview of its structure, tasks, and involved partners, as well as its timeline, deliverables, and milestones. He noted that WP5 technically begins in January 2024 and that the dedicated kick-off meeting is planned for March 2024, with the exact date still to be finalised. He then introduced the pipeline for Task 5.1, outlining key uncertainties and showcasing the added value of the project building on top of existing work in the pipeline’s schematic, which will inform ongoing work. Dr Sanderson followed with sub-task 5.1.1, focusing on uncertainties due to infilling assumptions, illustrating the associated challenges through various figures. Dr Mittal then presented sub-task 5.1.2, which will explore parametric and structural uncertainties in OpenSCM emulators, and briefly mentioned sub-task 5.1.3, concerning comparative analysis of land-use productivity between land models and IAMs. Dr Peters added that Deliverable 5.1, which defines the scenario space, will be discussed in more detail at</p>	<p>Discuss on the date of the WP5 kick-off meeting</p>	<p>All WP5 partners</p>

	<p>the kick-off meeting. A discussion ensued with Dr Mittal and Dr Sanderson on the interaction of model runs with AR6, including the possibility of using the AR6 database for consistency and enrichment. Moving on, Dr Peters introduced Task 5.2, which focuses on climate impacts and adaptation, presenting the upcoming steps through a schematic flow and outlining the role of modelling and assessment within this task. Task 5.3 was then addressed, examining uncertainties along the “bumpy road” to net-zero, where Dr Peters and Dr Mittal detailed the points of overlap with IAM COMPACT while also clarifying differences in framing and approach. Prof Pye presented Task 5.4, “Stretching the Frontiers,” and described its four sub-tasks, the partners leading each one, and the way the work will build on results from WP4. Dr Nikas then briefly introduced Task 5.5, clarifying that while this task starts formally in December 2024, some preparatory insight is already being gathered due to many partners' experience in other projects. Task 5.6 was outlined by Dr Peters, who described its focus on conducting a meta-analysis of scenario risks. Dr Mittal and Dr Sanderson contributed to the discussion, questioning how such risks could be meaningfully identified and integrated into the broader modelling framework. To conclude, Dr Koasidis and Mr Engel initiated a clarification on the division of work between Tasks 4.6 and 5.4, to which Dr Peters responded that Task 4.6 is primarily about model development, while Task 5.4 concerns the application and stretching of those tools into frontier research.</p>		
<p>WP6</p>	<p>Dr Koasidis and Dr Xexakis presented the progress and planning for WP6, outlining its structure, associated tasks, and timeline through a detailed Gantt chart and a list of deliverables. They introduced the project’s modelling data visualiser, which currently exists in a basic form based on the IPCC template. This tool is expected to evolve as part of the I²AM PARIS platform’s processing pipeline—where it will integrate with vetting tools—but it will also remain accessible as a standalone application. A discussion followed with Dr Mittal on minimising validation time; Dr Xexakis proposed breaking down large .csv files into smaller units for quicker processing, and Dr Koasidis noted that oversized model output files could also impede the tool’s performance. Dr Xexakis then introduced a new data entry process embedded in the platform, which features an upgraded database schema, automated data input via templates, and is built on an API framework. He also announced the upcoming Content Management System, which will give users a graphical interface to access platform data and allow registered contributors to upload new content. The presentation continued with an outline of WP6’s development pipelines, with an emphasis on upcoming steps. Dr Koasidis explained</p>		

	<p>that many modelling teams are still in the development phase and not yet dependent on the pipelines, but that teams should prepare for next phases, such as setting up GitHub repositories. Dr Xexakis also described the platform's validation routines, highlighting the types of checks and controls already available. He then updated the consortium on the project's participation in external communities of practice, noting published papers and posters, and listing collaborations with groups such as ECMF, IAMC, GCIMS, and openmod. Additionally, the consortium has engaged with IIASA, WRI, and Climate Action Data 2.0 to coordinate data platform activities, with further engagement possibilities mentioned, including ETSAP, EMF, OpTIMUS, and EFECT. Dr Xexakis also reminded the consortium about the upcoming update to the Open Data Management Plan in May, with Dr Koasidis adding that templates for Zenodo uploads are already available and that ICCS will contact partners to gather data. Later, Dr Peters and Dr Xexakis discussed the platform's validation code, which is based on PyAM, and Dr Boitier raised an issue related to variable naming, prompting a brief exchange. Finally, responding to a question from Dr Jan Ivar Korsbakken (CICERO), Dr Xexakis confirmed that recent updates to the platform would be shared soon.</p>		
WP7	<p>Regarding WP7, Dr Xexakis briefed the consortium on the WP's objectives, a Gantt chart and the timeline of Tasks, deliverables and milestones, and then proceeded to summarise the progress of Task 7.1 and present the Task's next steps, focusing on the need for more content. Afterwards, he continued by presenting Task 7.2, regarding the project's CDE plan, which will be updated the following May. In this context, he mentioned the project's synergies as well as the contacts that have taken place with other communities of practice. Moreover, he summarised the progress in the project's social media accounts, the project's participation in conferences and the future steps on this matter. In this context, Dr Koasidis mentioned that there is an invitation for the EGU conference with a deadline of the 10th of January 2024; in this conference, Dr Mittal and Dr Jon Sampedro (BC3) will host a session. Next, Dr Xexakis presented Task 7.3, briefing the partners on its KPIs (e.g., social media followers) and on its expected outcomes/results (policy, academia and society-wise). Lastly, Dr Nikas, Dr Peters and Dr Xexakis discussed the idea of opening DIAMOND social media accounts on other platforms as well (without abandoning the ones that the project is already engaging in), such as BlueSky, since the energy community is moving away from X (previously known as Twitter).</p>		
SAB Session	<p>The last session of the GA meeting's first day was the SAB session, which started with Dr Nikas thanking the SAB members for their attendance. He, then, briefed the SAB on</p>		

the major developments in each WP, focusing on the scientific outreach of the project, commenting on latest papers and the project's presence in modelling conferences. He also summarised the enhancements of the I²AM PARIS platform. Next, the discussion focused on WP2 and stakeholder engagement issues, such as the influence/interest of stakeholders on climate action. Following, members of the SAB and Dr Nikas discussed some insights from the *Joule* paper, focusing on energy demand trends and the study's main target, which was to inform people about the available pathways.

Afterwards, they discussion focused on the level of interaction that the consortium has with the EC. Dr Nikas was also asked if the EC is driving research towards specific directions, with him replying that the EC officers mainly provide feedback on innovative actions and not on the research's direction.

From a stakeholder engagement perspective, Dr Briers and Dr Vienni-Baptista delved into some details regarding the transdisciplinary approach that the project is using, with the discussion with SAB members surrounding the complexity of the endeavour. Dr Hermwille indicated that in a project they lead they bring practitioners together to discuss their problems and the solutions they use and then, the project's team adopts these insights in their research. Mr Cassolà mentioned that DIAMOND partners are eager to receive stakeholder feedback and are preparing to apply all their knowledge in the field.

Then, the discussion moved to WP3 and model development. On this subject, questions were raised on whether the consortium uses a centralised way to document the work in the used models. Dr Nikas and Dr Xexakis replied that each model has its own pipeline but the project aims to enhance all existing pipelines and add specific elements.

Following, Dr Mittal briefly presented WPs 4 and 5 describing their aims, mentioning that WP4 focuses on incorporating various aspects into the 6 core models, whereas WP5 examines the implementation of several modelling scenarios. Next, Dr Koasidis briefed the SAB on the objectives of WP6, focusing on the project's aim to have as open processes as possible.

From the SAB members, the first point raised was the influence/interest of stakeholders with Dr Briers replying that examining the influence/interest of each stakeholder for specific project tasks can be very helpful in determining at what level a stakeholder should be involved in future activities. The second point raised was on feasibility, focusing on the inclusion of pace speeds in future modelling work, with Dr Nikas and Dr Mittal replying that one of the studies under discussion aimed to examine how a specific framework

	<p>functions. They also mentioned that the consortium aims to incorporate pace speeds in future studies.</p> <p>Ending the session, Dr Nikas thanked the SAB members for their attendance and encouraged them to provide further feedback.</p>		
Day II			
Synopsis of Day I and Aims of Day II	Dr Nikas summarised the discussions of the 1 st day and presented the agenda for Day II.		
What's next for stakeholder engagement?	<p>Dr Briers began her presentation on the first phase of WP2 by encouraging open participation to foster a more interactive discussion. She then outlined the aims of the session, presenting the structure of the three stakeholder engagement phases, their interlinkages, associated deliverables, and relevant reports. She also explained the iterative approach between WP2, DIAMOND partners, and stakeholders, highlighting how stage 3 of Phase 1 began that day, while Phase 2 is set to start in May. She concluded by listing actions connected to the sessions planned for the second day of the General Assembly. A discussion followed between Dr Mittal and Dr Briers on how the iterative process would apply across work packages. Dr Briers explained that workshops would be theme-based, potentially linked to specific WPs or broader topics, and that WP2 partners would consider their networks when deciding participants. She then updated the consortium on two expert interviews for the Future Models Manual scheduled for mid-January and outlined WP2 actions planned for March and April. She also mentioned 15 prioritised co-design actions grouped into three themes, providing examples aligned with project WPs. A discussion on the Future Models Manual followed, where Dr Nikas praised efforts to make modelling accessible to citizens, with Dr Xexakis and Dr Mittal noting similar outreach initiatives in other countries. Dr Xexakis and Dr Briers then discussed citizen participation, agreeing on the value of involving representative groups to better connect the project with the public. Mr Cassolà then presented the second phase of WP2, which includes a multi-stakeholder process structured around three aspects, and described the knowledge integration process, organised into four steps under a Common Frame. He also outlined stakeholder types (in three groups), the mapping process, the main goals of the stakeholder database, and categories of foresight workshops, including both expert- and citizen-oriented approaches. He and Dr van de Ven discussed tentative timelines for the workshops, while Dr Koasidis and Mr Cassolà explored their possible topics. Dr Mittal and Mr Cassolà then touched on the overlapping themes of WPs 4 and 5 and how they might be addressed in parallel sessions. Dr Nikas urged the consortium</p>		

	<p>to keep the stakeholder database current, noting that repeated engagement rounds can reduce participation. This prompted a broader discussion among Dr Briers, Dr Nikas, Dr Koasidis, and Mr Cassolà on whether stakeholder groups should be larger or smaller, weighing the respective advantages.</p>		
<p>Understanding stakeholder engagement expectations</p>	<p>Dr Briers opened the session by explaining that each WP would have 20 minutes to present their stakeholder engagement expectations, followed by 10 minutes of discussion, and noted that the third session would focus on WP-specific actions. Dr Mittal suggested also addressing overlaps between WPs. Dr van de Ven presented the linkages between WPs 2 and 3, highlighting relevant actions, deliverables, and timelines, and showing how core models interact with stakeholders. He summarised modelling team needs and upcoming steps, noting the importance of knowing stakeholder types, which led to a brief exchange with Dr Mittal on potential bilateral meetings.</p> <p>Dr Mittal then raised the issue of stakeholder surveys across WPs 3, 4 and 5, asking if they fall under stakeholder engagement and who would design them. Dr Koasidis proposed a consistent approach unless a task requires a different one. Dr Briers said ETH is not a survey expert but would like to be involved in reporting and proposed ETH lead workshop organisation instead, which Dr Nikas and Dr Mittal supported.</p> <p>Next, Dr Mittal outlined WP4’s engagement expectations, focusing on insights needed per task, overlaps with WP5, and interactions planned for finance, labour, and consumption. She noted WP4 is at an early stage and needs may evolve. Mr Cassolà responded that ISINNOVA would aim to reflect these needs in stakeholder interactions. Dr Peters followed with WP5, describing stakeholder co-creation of scenarios, expectations per task, and planned surveys and workshops. He and Dr Briers discussed aligning WP4 and WP5 timelines, with Dr Mittal adding that workshops would start in 2024, possibly continuing into 2025.</p> <p>Dr Peters and Dr Mittal also discussed the scenario filtering process and gaps in AR6, with Dr Sanderson suggesting broader scenario exploration. They agreed on the importance of familiarising stakeholders with uncertainty, which led to further discussion on how stakeholders perceive uncertainty across climate, economics, and SSPs. Dr Mittal noted that input here can help improve scenario design. This continued into a short exchange on holding a workshop focused on this topic. Dr Xexakis proposed organising both general and targeted workshops based on available resources, and Dr Briers agreed. Finally, Prof Pye and Dr Briers briefly discussed approaches to familiarising stakeholders with the 1.5°C target.</p>		

<p>Designing our engagements</p>	<p>The final session began with Dr Briers explaining that it would focus on aligning stakeholder engagement actions with WPs through a matchmaking process, followed by timeline planning. She presented 15 actions grouped into 3 themes, assessed by 20 respondents for importance, feasibility, and WP involvement. Action 1 emerged as the highest priority.</p> <p>Dr Nikas and Dr Mittal briefly discussed incorporating stakeholder feedback into models, with Dr Briers noting that informing stakeholders their input was used is often useful and sufficient. Discussions followed on combining certain actions, highlighting concerns over the complexity of some. Dr Mittal suggested prioritising actions related to the ones outlined in the Grant Agreement and forming a secondary “wish list.”</p> <p>The group also discussed working with existing communities of practice. Prof Pye, Dr Briers, and Dr Mittal addressed how to better engage them, while Dr Nikas noted that relationships already exist. Dr Vienni-Baptista advised strengthening existing communities instead of creating new ones and suggested coordination with sister projects. Dr Xexakis mentioned an existing contact list.</p> <p>Dr Briers encouraged partners to link actions to project tasks and to identify overlapping or mergeable actions. ETH will group actions based on partner input and define suitable engagement formats. A discussion followed on the roles of workshops, with ISINNOVA leading those for WP4, and ETH focusing on WPs 3 and 5.</p> <p>Further, the relevance of each action to research questions and WP priorities was discussed. Mr Cassolà noted that the first workshop set aligns with Action 1. Dr Vienni-Baptista added that ETH will be synthesising outcomes all workshops into a synthesis deliverable and that some discussion topics may only emerge through the additional actions.</p> <p>She also clarified that ETH’s goal is to support the consortium in selecting preferred actions. Ms Sechi and Mr Cassolà briefly touched on stakeholder mapping and expectations. Dr Nikas and Dr Briers then discussed how action-task links would be recorded, with Briers urging everyone to review and complete the list.</p> <p>Finally, Dr Briers, Prof Sanders, Dr Peters, and Prof Pye discussed relevant actions link to WPs 3–5, highlighting implications for model design and audience targeting.</p>		
<p>Closing discussion and next steps</p>	<p>Closing the discussion, Dr Vienni-Baptista summarised the previous discussion points and then stated that the actions have two dimensions: one is related to the different roles of stakeholders and the second one aims to make stakeholder engagement more robust.</p> <p>Next, Dr Peters and Dr Briers had a discussion on the flexibility of organising a workshop, regarding its topic, venue (physical or online), the time given to invite stakeholders, the</p>		

	<p>heterogeneity of the stakeholders participating and the format of the event.</p> <p>Following this, Dr Peters, Dr Briers and Dr Vienni-Baptista discussed the timeline of these actions, agreeing that these actions will probably take place during the 2nd year of the project, starting from the following May.</p> <p>Next, Dr Peters briefed the consortium about the kick-off meeting for WP5.</p> <p>Lastly, Dr Nikas informed the consortium that the actions file with notes during the meeting was uploaded and encouraged partners to refine it.</p>		
Wrap-up	<p>Finally, Dr Nikas thanked all the partners for attending the meeting and thanked ETH and ISINNOVA partners for their great contribution to the sessions on the 2nd day of the meeting.</p>		

3.2 Executive Board Meeting – 28 February 2024

3.2.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Wednesday, 28 February 2024
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - Request to keep the contact list updated
 - WP2: Codising
 - Summary of D2.4 takeaways
 - Mapping of stakeholder actions to tasks
 - Updates on the stakeholder database
 - Progress towards D2.2 (April 2024)
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - Overall progress in model development and short updates for all six core models:
 - OMNIA
 - CLEWs-EU
 - GCAM-Europe
 - NEMESIS-World
 - OPEN-PROM
 - GEMINI-E3 EU
 - Updates from bilateral calls (e.g., GEMINI-E3 - NEMESIS; CLEWs - visualisation)
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Progress on WP4 module/task discussions
 - Updates from bilateral calls (e.g., GEMINI-E3 - labour; CLEWs - behavioural surveys)
 - WP5: Apply & Explore
 - Updates on scenario pipeline uncertainties
 - WP6: Open
 - Progress on the supporting tools under development
 - Updates on the I2AM PARIS platform
 - Planning for WP2-prescribed actions
 - WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - Newsletters
 - Social media

2. Any other business

3.2.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS

2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
4	Natasha Frilingou	ICCS
5	Eleftheria Zisarou	ICCS
6	Anastasis Giannousakis	ICCS
7	Ioannis Tolios	ICCS
8	Russell Horowitz	BC3
9	Dirk-Jan Van de Ven	BC3
10	Jon Sampedro	BC3
11	Claudia Rodes	BC3
12	Ben Sanderson	CICERO
13	Ida Sognnaes	CICERO
14	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
15	Tomasso Pilon	E4SMA
16	Sonja Sechi	E4SMA
17	Maurizio Gargiulo	E4SMA
18	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
19	Andrés Ramos Galán	COMILLAS
20	Sandra Lumbreras	COMILLAS
21	Maria dek Socorro Gómez Perez	COMILLAS
22	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
23	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
24	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
25	Mark Sanders	UM
26	Marie Pied	ESMIA
27	Stephanie Briers	ETH
28	Adam Hawkes	Imperial
29	Leigh Martindale	Imperial
30	Sergey Maximov	UCL
31	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
32	Marc Vielle	EPFL

Minutes: Main issues discussed			
Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	The meeting commenced with Dr Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) greeting the consortium and briefing them on the agenda. Related to WP1, he reiterated items and requests discussed during the GA, crucially regarding keeping the internal contact lists up to date.		
WP2	Dr Briers opened the discussion on the outputs of D2.4 and related stakeholder engagement tasks. She presented an Excel file mapping stakeholder actions to WPs and ETH's involvement, urging WP leaders to review and comment in a proposed half-hour meeting. The file will be shared via weekly updates, with Dr Koasidis suggesting proper folder placement. Dr Briers highlighted key insights from D2.4,	Take a look at the stakeholder actions file	All partners
		Provide feedback to ETH	WP leaders

	<p>noting stakeholders’ awareness of project progress and familiarity with the transdisciplinary process, recommending all partners read the executive summary. Nikas indicated that the deliverable features great detail. Mr Cassolá reported that Phase 1 of the survey rolled out finished with over 70 responses (68 positive) and 58 interested to join in the workshops. He noted a possible second invitation round to improve discipline representation and shared that work on updating D2.1 is underway, focusing on providing a timeline for the upcoming workshops. UNIBAS and ISINNOVA plan meetings for synergy. Dr Koasidis noted that 58 engaged participants could form a solid core group especially if they are committed to continuous participations. He and Mr Cassolá also discussed modelling teams’ roles in April workshops, with Mr Cassolá promising an update by next week.</p>	<p>Disseminate the file through the weekly update</p> <p>Inform the consortium about the April workshops</p>	<p>ICCS</p> <p>ISINNOVA</p>
WP3	<p>Ms Sonja Sechi (E4SMA) presented recent model enhancements: OMNIA improved energy balance and plans an energy demand workshop; GCAM-EU integrated Eurostat energy data; OPEN-PROM completed its data and energy module; GEMINI-EU advanced on hydrogen, pollutants, and carbon taxation; CLEWs-EU is adding transportation; NEMESIS progress remains limited. Dr Dirk-Jan van de Ven (BC3) updated on numerous bilateral meetings between modelling teams. Dr Sigit Perdana (EPFL) clarified meetings with non-modelling teams (e.g., UNIBAS, UM) and shared upcoming meeting plans. Dr Constantinos Taliotis (CYI) reported on discussions with HOLISTIC partners about results visualisation for CLEWs-EU, aiming to develop an interface similar to EU-CALC. Dr Marc Vielle (EPFL) noted ongoing work on EU-CALC at EPFL and offered contact. Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) emphasised inspiration from EU-CALC rather than direct use, supported by Dr Koasidis, who also saw benefit in engaging the EU-CALC team for stakeholder work. Dr Koasidis stressed the challenge of tracking bilateral meetings, requesting brief summaries be sent to ICCS management for better coordination. He suggested such meetings could contribute to WP2 actions if relevant.</p>	<p>Communicate with the EU-CALC team</p> <p>Send a short description of bilateral meetings to ICCS</p>	<p>EPFL, HOLISTIC</p> <p>All partners</p>
WP4	<p>Dr Nikas took the floor mentioning the many aspects of WP4 had already been discussed with Prof Adam Hawkes (Imperial) mentioning that this WP is now starting to have major progress since it started quite late according to the project’s timeline. Specifically, he stated that Tasks 4.1 and 4.4 just started, hence there is nothing to report. Lastly, he mentioned that the Milestone 7 report is on track.</p>		
WP5	<p>Then, Dr Ben Sanderson (CICERO) informed the partners that the kick-off meeting of WP5 will take place on the 14th of March 2024. He also mentioned that Dr Shivika Mittal (CICERO) and Dr Glen Peters (CICERO) had a meeting with the OMNIA team. Dr Sanderson also mentioned that CICERO is in</p>	<p>Solve the MAGPIE issue</p>	<p>CICERO, Imperial, ICCS</p>

	the process of writing a preliminary report on climate impacts and that a relevant paper led by Dr Mittal will be prepared by the end of March. Issues related to access and use of the MAgPIE model were discussed.		
WP6	<p>The discussion on WP6 commenced with Dr Koasidis discussing potential internal meetings and workshops regarding specific thematic areas.</p> <p>Dr Xexakis briefed the consortium on discussions with Dr Taliotis regarding the visualisation interface. Then, he briefed the partners on the progress of the I²AM PARIS interface, stating that a demonstration version would be soon available. He also mentioned that the interface allows users to easily modify the model documentation.</p>	<p>Improve the I²AM PARIS platform</p> <p>Focus on open data issues meetings</p>	<p>HOLISTIC</p> <p>All partners, ETH, ISINNOVA</p>
WP7	<p>Lastly, Dr Xexakis informed the consortium that the dissemination process is progressing successfully and stated that developing a tool similar to EUCALC can be a good strategy. He also proposed communicating with the WorldTrans project teams on potential synergies. In this context, Dr Koasidis asked the consortium to communicate with the ICCS and HOLISTIC teams if they participate in or host any conference that would need dissemination resources. The meeting concluded with Dr Nikas thanking all participants.</p>	<p>Contact HOLISTIC/ICCS on conferences for dissemination</p>	<p>All partners</p>

3.3 Executive Board Meeting – 27 March 2024

3.3.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Wednesday, 27 March 2024
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - Preparation of the next General Assembly
 - WP2: Codising
 - Planning of stakeholder actions from WPs/tasks
 - Updates on the stakeholder database
 - Progress towards D2.2 (April 2024)
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - Overall progress in model development and short updates for all six core models:
 - OMNIA
 - CLEWs-EU
 - GCAM-Europe
 - NEMESIS-World
 - OPEN-PROM
 - GEMINI-E3 EU
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Progress on WP4 modules/tasks:
 - Labour, finance, well-being
 - Behavioural surveys
 - Circular economy
 - Climate/physical impacts
 - WP5: Apply & Explore
 - Reflections on the WP5 kick-off meeting
 - WP6: Open
 - Progress on the supporting tools under development
 - Updates on the I2AM PARIS platform
 - WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - Newsletters
 - Social media
2. Any other business

3.3.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Thomas Nikolakakis	ICCS

4	Eleftheria Zisarou	ICCS
5	Anastasis Giannousakis	ICCS
6	Ioannis Tolios	ICCS
7	George Plessias	ICCS
8	Fotis Sioutas	ICCS
9	Dirk-Jan Van de Ven	BC3
10	Kurt Kratena	CESAR
11	Shivika Mittal	CICERO
12	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
13	Alessia Elia	E4SMA
14	Tomasso Pilon	E4SMA
15	Sonja Sechi	E4SMA
16	Maurizio Gargiulo	E4SMA
17	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
18	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
19	Marie Pied	ESMIA
20	Bianca Vienni-Baptista	ETH
21	Stephanie Briers	ETH
22	Adam Hawkes	Imperial
23	Leigh Martindale	Imperial
24	Vignesh Sridharan	Imperial
25	Steve Pye	UCL
26	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
27	Marc Vielle	EPFL

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	<p>Dr. Nikas (ICCS) opened the discussion about the upcoming General Assembly (GA) meeting, with Dr. Koasidis (ICCS) noting it will take place before the first reporting period and thanking EPFL for organizing the hybrid meeting in Lausanne. He shared that a draft logistics document, including hotel info, has been sent to partners and will be continuously updated, urging everyone to fill out the attendance spreadsheet. The agenda will focus mainly on the end of the first reporting period, with plans to include an SAB session. Dr. Perdana (EPFL) expressed the team's enthusiasm for hosting and reiterated the logistics details. When Dr. Mittal (CICERO) inquired about other events during the two-day meeting, Dr. Nikas replied that while some time might be allocated to additional ideas, the GA remains the priority. Dr. Koasidis mentioned a potential concurrent online workshop but saw no need to merge it with the GA. Dr. Nikas added that the agenda is still open for suggestions, with intentions to cover WP2 and host the SAB session, inviting members in person if possible. He requested that all partners prepare</p>	<p>Inform partners on physical attendance</p> <p>Prepare a draft agenda</p>	<p>EPFL on</p> <p>ICCS, EPFL</p> <p>All partners</p>

	<p>examples and deadlines for the WP1 session at the GA.</p> <p>Dr. Nikas stated that expectedly parts of the discussions during the GA will focus on the mid-term report and stressed the need to find an effective way to present progress for the interim report despite limited deliverables so far. Dr. Mittal asked for guidance on documenting modelling processes without sharing code, suggesting a brainstorming session during the GA. Dr. Nikas replied that the Commission prefers concise reports and that ICCS would share examples, with support from WP3 and WP4 leaders. They also discussed the GA meeting framework related to WP5 and stakeholder engagement. Dr. Nikas highlighted a busy June due to mid-term reporting and clarified the role of associated partners ICCS will contact partners by end of May with requests and a 3–4 week deadline.</p>		
WP2	<p>Mr. Daniel Cassolá (ISINNOVA) updated the consortium on finalising the stakeholder engagement strategy (D2.1) and mentioned upcoming workshop requirements, with the date to be confirmed soon. He noted that stakeholders will be informed about the foresight and scenario workshops. Dr. Stephanie Briers (ETH) added that WP2 action meetings are ongoing with other WP leaders, highlighting coordination with WP6 on webinars, WP5 on relevant actions, and WP3 on the ISINNOVA workshop and its links to WP5. Dr. Koasidis emphasised that the timeline of scheduling the requirements workshop is crucial for an efficient preparation—if the workshop is to take place on May workshop, a clear workshop structure and timely working documents are necessary as well as invitations be sent before Catholic Easter. He also reminded that WPs 3, 4, and 5 must meet their deadlines on research questions to ensure the work remains stakeholder-driven.</p>	<p>Finalise D2.1</p> <p>Inform stakeholders of the upcoming workshops</p> <p>Communicate with WP leaders for WP2 actions</p>	<p>ISINNOVA</p> <p>ISINNOVA</p> <p>ETH, WP leaders</p>
WP3	<p>Next, Ms Sonja Sechi (E4SMA) briefed the partners on the progress of each of the six core models. The NEMESIS model team is preparing a simplified version of the model so they can test its properties. In the CLEWs-EU model, the energy module is almost complete and that the land & water module is under development. The GEMINI model team is currently working on the IPCC template and is also running some preliminary tests. The modularisation of the OPEN-PROM model has begun in order to provide simple and extended versions of each module. Regarding the GCAM-Europe model, energy balances and income groups are finalised, whereas the buildings’ energy balance is being extended. Lastly, the OMNIA model team started implementing the renewal potential, data for which is provided by CICERO colleagues. Then, she informed the consortium that two soft-linking meetings had been arranged and that E4SMA awaited CICERO’s reply regarding the soft-linking of their model.</p>		

	<p>Before the discussion moved to WP4, Dr Dirk-Jan van de Ven (BC3) proposed that some research questions from WP3 could be included in the requirements workshop, stating that he would soon communicate some needs.</p>		
WP4	<p>Prof Adam Hawkes (Imperial) stated that there is not much to report on Tasks 4.1, 4.5 and 4.6 and that they are in progress. On the other hand, the other tasks, as expected, have not kicked off yet. Next, Prof Steve Pye (UCL) mentioned that they are improving the ENGAGE model, focusing on doing parallel work with OMNIA. He also suggested starting a discussion on whether the project can also include models that are not mentioned in the Grant Agreement. In this context, he and Dr Nikas had a discussion on which other teams can participate beyond the ones already mentioned in the Grant Agreement, focusing on the intercomparison study in Task 5.4. In this context, Dr Mittal agreed with Prof Pye and encouraged teams to join in circular economy issues with their models. Dr Nikas added the GA meeting can be a good forum to engage on Prof Pye’s idea.</p>	<p>Discuss the inclusion of additional models</p>	<p>UCL, ICCS</p>
WP5	<p>Following this, Dr Mittal informed the partners that there are already two meetings arranged regarding WP5; one will focus on Task 4.2 regarding the climate impact issues with Oxford partners and the other one will be related to Task 5.1 regarding the development of silicon. Apart from these, another meeting with Dr Briers will take place to discuss the info required for the stakeholder workshops. Dr Mittal continued by reminding the consortium that an e-mail has been sent regarding facing uncertainties and the establishment of a relevant framework. Moreover, she stated that they would return to modelling teams on limitations to map research questions, indicating that a lot of work has to be done before stakeholder meetings.</p> <p>She also informed the consortium that a literature review on climate impacts will be prepared by mid-April, aiming to detect gaps to improve the project’s models. In this context, a survey will be sent to all modelling teams asking how their models can be improved and whether they can incorporate adaptation issues.</p>	<p>Prepare a set of frameworks regarding uncertainties</p> <p>Fill in a survey regarding climate impacts and climate change adaptation</p>	<p>CICERO</p> <p>All modelling partners</p>
WP6	<p>Next, Dr Koasidis briefed the partners on HOLISTIC’s work on facilitating the presentation of different versions of models in the platform. In this context, he mentioned that they will ask for feedback on the appearance of the updated version, with the aim of integrating the received comments. Then, he started a discussion on WP2 actions related to WPs 6 and 7, focusing on webinars that will be organised during 2025. In this context, he mentioned that thematic workshops based on the expertise of different partners will be organised, aiming to enhance the project’s understanding and communication of key topics. He concluded by mentioning that an e-mail requesting ideas for these workshops would</p>	<p>Improving the I²AM PARIS platform.</p> <p>Organise workshops and webinars related to WP6</p>	<p>HOLISTIC</p> <p>HOLISTIC, ETH, ISINNOVA</p>

	be sent shortly.		
WP7	Lastly, Dr Koasidis informed the consortium that the implementation of the CDE plan is going well and that there are no major updates on WP7.		

3.4 Executive Board Meeting – 24 April 2024

3.4.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting

Wednesday, 24 April 2024

14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - Updates on the organisation of the next General Assembly (at EPFL in Lausanne, CH)
 - Quality management-related prompts
 - WP2: Codesing
 - Progress in the co-creation phases
 - Requirements workshop (May 2024)
 - Status of D2.2 (April 2024)
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - Overall progress in model development and short updates for all six core models:
 - OMNIA
 - CLEWs-EU
 - GCAM-Europe
 - NEMESIS-World
 - OPEN-PROM
 - GEMINI-E3 EU
 - Updates on the collection of WP3-related research questions
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Progress on WP4 modules/tasks:
 - Labour, finance, well-being
 - Behavioural surveys
 - Circular economy
 - Climate/physical impacts
 - WP5: Apply & Explore
 - • Updates on the collection of WP5-related research questions and information
 - WP6: Open
 - Status update on D6.2
 - Progress on the supporting tools under development
 - Updates on the I2AM PARIS platform
 - WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - Status update on D7.3
 - Newsletters
 - Social media
 - EGU aftermath (experiences, impressions, etc.)
2. Any other business

3.4.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
4	Fotis Sioutas	ICCS
5	Anastasis Giannousakis	ICCS
6	Ioannis Tolios	ICCS
7	Claudia Rodes	BC3
8	Russell Horowitz	BC3
9	Dirk-Jan Van de Ven	BC3
10	Glen Peters	CICERO
11	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
12	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
13	Alessia Elia	E4SMA
14	Tomasso Pilon	E4SMA
15	Sonja Sechi	E4SMA
16	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
17	Sara Lumbreras	COMILLAS
18	Maria del Socorro Gómez Pérez	COMILLAS
19	Andrés Ramos Galán	COMILLAS
20	Luis Olmos Camacho	COMILLAS
21	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
22	Carlo Sessa	ISINNOVA
23	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
24	Paul Zagamé	SEURECO
25	Mark Sanders	UM
26	Marie Pied	ESMIA
27	Bianca Vienni-Baptista	ETH
28	Stephanie Briers	ETH
29	Leigh Martindale	Imperial
30	James Price	UCL
31	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
32	Marc Vielle	EPFL

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	Dr. Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) opened the meeting by welcoming the consortium and reminding everyone of the logistics file shared by EPFL for the upcoming General Assembly (GA) meeting. Dr. Konstantinos Koasidis (ICCS) noted that a draft agenda is available and open to minor changes, particularly concerning the SAB session, and reminded all partners attending in person to complete the attendance spreadsheet. Dr. Sigit Perdana (EPFL) informed	Fill in the attendance spreadsheet	All partners

	<p>participants that EPFL is testing Zoom’s hybrid capabilities and will share the link once confirmed. Dr. Nikas requested to ensure the session is recorded, and encouraged physical attendance as there is still room at the venue. He then turned to WP1 and the Quality Management Process, asking partners to inform the management team of any expected delays in the internal deadlines of deliverables so internal reviewers can be informed. Dr. Koasidis encouraged volunteers for internal reviewing and explained that updated deliverables follow the same process as original ones. He also noted some deliverables have different numbering in the Grant Agreement compared to the proposal. Dr. Nikas concluded by stating that updated deliverables should build on their previous versions.</p>		
WP2	<p>Dr. Stephanie Briers (ETH) informed the consortium that ETH is reviewing research questions for WP5, to be discussed at the GA meeting in May, and will follow a similar approach for WP3. ETH is also gathering data for upcoming stakeholder workshops. She, Dr. Nikas, and Dr. Perdana briefly discussed resolving potential technical issues for virtual participation in the GA meeting. Mr. Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) then presented updates on the second phase of stakeholder engagement, including progress on D2.2, which builds on D2.1 and is under review. He outlined Task 2.3.1, focusing on foresight workshops planned between June and November 2024, covering IAM requirements and scenario design, and Task 2.3.2 on value-driven foresight and climate-friendly practice workshops. He also shared updates on the stakeholder database and survey results, with 73 responses—53 of whom expressed further interest in engagement. These were mapped by capacity, expertise, and IAM familiarity, showing diverse representation. He concluded with next steps for the Requirements workshop, to be discussed further at the GA meeting. Dr. Briers then mentioned Ms. Victoria Herbig’s presentation at the EGU conference and suggested a session to present its findings within the project, which Dr. Nikas and Dr. Koasidis supporting the idea. Dr. Nikas and Mr. Cassolà discussed how to inform the consortium about the upcoming requirements workshop, with Mr. Carlo Sessa (ISINNOVA) proposing it as a GA meeting agenda item. Ms. Sonja Sechi (E4SMA) requested all modelling teams complete a spreadsheet and suggested coordinating a deadline with ISINNOVA. Dr. Koasidis concluded that due to the tight timeline, all workshop details should be finalised during the GA meeting, with Mr. Sessa agreeing and confirming early preparations.</p>	<p>Review the research questions of WP3 and WP5</p> <p>Organise the foresight workshops</p> <p>Finalise the details regarding the workshop in June</p> <p>Fill in the spreadsheet prepared by E4SMA</p>	<p>ETH</p> <p>ISINNOVA</p> <p>ISINNOVA</p> <p>All modelling teams</p>
WP3	<p>Next, Ms Sechi proceeded to WP3, briefing the consortium on the advancements made regarding the six core models. She began with NEMESIS, for which a simplified version for testing purposes is being developed. Moreover, the NEMESIS</p>	<p>Provide feedback regarding WP3 research questions</p>	<p>All modelling teams</p>

	<p>team had a meeting with partners from CESAR. Next, the CLEWs-EU modelling team has made the first successful attempt to aggregate the energy and land & water modules. Moreover, they are proceeding with calibrating their modules. The GEMINI team is working on the European section of the model and marking pollutants following IPCC templates. They have also met with CESAR partners. Regarding the OPEN-PROM model progress is made on the supporting tools. GCAM-Europe is also being enhanced focusing on finalising the work around Eurostat's energy balance. Lastly, the OMNIA model team participated in a workshop on demand projection with colleagues from WP5. They also had meetings on soft-linking their model, notably with ENGAGE. They have also improved the regionalisation of OMNIA and proceeded to enhance its power section, in communication with UCL. In conclusion, Ms Sechi requested that all WP3 modelling teams provide feedback regarding the research questions.</p>		
WP4	<p>The discussion moved to WP4 and Dr Sara Lumbreras (COMILLAS) briefed the consortium on the progress of OpenTEPES. She demonstrated the interconnections between WP4 and Tasks in WP3 as well as the pipeline of the work. She mentioned that focus will be given to linking OpenTEPES with OMNIA and showcased some linkage examples. In this context, Dr Lumbreras and Ms Sechi had a discussion on the way that the models can be connected since it is not such a straightforward process and they agreed to arrange a bilateral meeting to engage in this matter.</p> <p>Next, Dr Glen Peters (CICERO) informed the partners of the progress of Task 4.4, which focuses on working on calibrations and the METEOR model.</p> <p>Prof Mark Sanders (UM) quickly updated the consortium on the work done by their team related to WP4. Dr Nikas concluded the discussion on WP4 mentioning that Prof Kurt Kratena (CESAR) will upload a presentation in the project's SharePoint and that other partners also had updates to report but due to the meeting's limited time they would not do it.</p>	<p>Arrange a meeting between OMNIA and OpenTEPES teams</p>	<p>E4SMA, COMILLAS</p>
WP5	<p>Next, Dr Peters summarised the progress of WP5, informing the partners about the kick-off meeting that took place the previous March. He also mentioned that they are collecting data for each Task regarding research questions. He concluded by mentioning that his team intends to have a relevant session in the GA meeting.</p>		
WP6	<p>Then, Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) briefed the consortium on the meeting that took place with partners from the WorldTrans project. In this meeting, the WorldTrans team demonstrated an interest in policy platforms and expressed their willingness to create opportunities for synergies.</p> <p>Afterwards, he also mentioned that HOLISTIC had a meeting with members of the MAIA project, which aims to help</p>		

	<p>HORIZON projects disseminate their insights. This meeting can also be considered an action related to WP7 as well. Moreover, he informed the consortium of the enhancements of the I²AM PARIS platform, also stating that during the GA meeting, HOLISTIC will provide more details on how partners can contribute to upcoming webinars.</p>		
WP7	<p>In conclusion, Dr Nikas mentioned that the project had a sufficient representation in the EGU conference and thanked everyone for attending the meeting.</p>		

3.5 Executive Board Meeting – 19 June 2024

3.5.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Wednesday, 19 June 2024
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - Preparation for the review report:
 - Technical Aspects including templates
 - Financial Requirements
 - Q&A
 - Interim review meeting
 - Reflections on Lausanne GA & SAB feedback
 - Reflections on RP1
 - WP2: Codesing
 - Foresight Workshops
 - Updates on the planning of multi-stakeholder group discussions
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - Overall progress in model development and short updates for all six core models:
 - OMNIA
 - CLEWs-EU
 - GCAM-Europe
 - NEMESIS-World
 - OPEN-PROM
 - GEMINI-E3 EU
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Progress on WP4 modules/tasks:
 - Labour, finance, well-being
 - Behavioural surveys
 - Circular economy
 - Climate/physical impacts
 - WP5: Apply & Explore
 - •Updates on Task 5.1 & the preparation of the novel scenario space
 - WP6: Open
 - Preparation on the thematic workshops and survey to brainstorm ideas
 - Progress on the supporting tools under development
 - Updates on the I2AM PARIS platform
 - WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - Status update on D7.3
 - Newsletters
 - Social media
 - IAMC & ECEMP submissions
2. Any other business

3.5.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
4	Thomas Nikolakakis	ICCS
5	Anastasis Giannousakis	ICCS
6	Ioannis Tolios	ICCS
7	Claudia Rodes	BC3
8	Jon Sampedro	BC3
9	Shivika Mittal	CICERO
10	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
11	Alessia Elia	E4SMA
12	Tomasso Pilon	E4SMA
13	Sonja Sechi	E4SMA
14	Maurizio Gargiulo	E4SMA
15	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
16	Maria del Socorro Gómez Pérez	COMILLAS
17	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
18	Pierre Le Mouël	SEURECO
19	Mark Sanders	UM
20	Marie Pied	ESMIA
21	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
22	Marc Vielle	EPFL
23	Stephanie Briers	ETH
24	Lukas Engel	UNIBAS
25	Maro Malliaroudaki	Imperial
26	Michael Obersteiner	Oxford
27	Alvaro Calzadilla	UCL

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	Dr. Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) opened the meeting by welcoming the consortium and introducing Dr. Maro Malliaroudaki (Imperial), who briefly presented her modelling background. He then gave an update on WP1, announcing that an evaluator has been assigned and that the interim review meeting will take place on 27 September 2024, with participation of WP leaders and selected task leaders in case questions arise on specific modelling matters. A rehearsal will be held earlier in September, and a Doodle poll will be sent out soon to allow scheduling before the summer holidays. Dr. Nikas reminded partners to update their SyGMA profiles and noted that associated partners should coordinate with ICCS for access. He and Dr. Mittal discussed the review process. He noted the GA meeting in Lausanne was successful, with the	Prepare a Doodle poll for the presentations’ rehearsal for the interim review meeting	ICCS
		Update SyGMA profile regarding research personnel	All partners
		Prepare technical and financial	WP leaders and all partners

	only change being the new September date for the Requirements workshop. WP1 and WP6 technical reports are now in the repository, and other WP leaders were reminded to prepare their reports. Dr. Koasidis outlined internal deadlines: 28 June for technical reports and 5 July for financial ones, ahead of the 30 July official deadline. Finally, Dr. Mittal and Dr. Nikas discussed how to present WP linkages.	reports	respectively
WP2	Dr. Stephanie Briers (ETH) updated the consortium on a bilateral meeting with CICERO regarding the co-design and grouping of WP3 and WP5 research question modules. She plans to analyse these groups and design the modules by summer, encouraging modelling teams to explore a few themes of interest to stakeholders. Mr. Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) thanked partners for their feedback on the Requirements Workshop preparatory material, highlighting CYI's suggestion to reduce the number of questions and E4SMA's offer to lead the first session on model development strategy. Dr. Sonja Sechi (E4SMA) confirmed their support, and a bilateral meeting between E4SMA and ISINNOVA was proposed. Dr. Koasidis stressed that ISINNOVA should finalise the workshop's structure and timeline, noting a scheduling conflict for ICCS colleagues on September 13. Mr. Cassolà agreed on the urgency of settling key issues to reach out to stakeholders before summer. Dr. Mittal confirmed CICERO's readiness to support, and Mr. Cassolà expressed ISINNOVA's flexibility. He also noted that WP3 research question refinement can now begin.	Co-design and group modules for research questions from WP3 and WP5 Organise a bilateral meeting for the 1 st session of the Requirements workshop	ETH ISINNOVA, E4SMA
WP3	Next, Dr Sechi and Dr Jon Sampedro updated the consortium on the core models' development progress. Then, Dr Nikas, Dr Koasidis, and Dr Sechi discussed technical reporting for model development as part of the interim report. Dr Mittal and Dr Koasidis also had a short discussion on what the technical report of tasks that have not started yet should include, agreeing that a short description and basic planning are sufficient.	Prepare technical reports for each model	Modelling partners
WP4	Dr. Malliaroudaki noted she is still mapping the project linkages and proposed discussing next steps with Task leaders. Dr. Alvaro Calzadilla (UCL) then presented Task 4.1 progress on circular economy and related linkages. For Task 4.2, Dr. Mittal reported no major updates on MAGPIE and OMNIA but shared that a METEOR pipeline was discussed with the WorldTrans project, and a survey will be sent to WP3 modelling teams. Prof. Mark Sanders (UM) suggested synthesising the Lausanne work and mentioned Mr. O'Connell's upcoming visit to EPFL to advance linkages. He added that Ms. Serebriakova will follow up on the remaining UM topics. On Task 4.6, Mr. Lukas Engel (UNIBAS) said behavioural experiments are ongoing, with coordination efforts underway with UM and CESAR. Finally, Ms. Gómez Pérez (COMILLAS) reported ongoing coordination between	Prepare a survey for WP3 modelling teams Synthesise the GA work	CICERO UM

	COMILLAS and BC3 on aligning GCAM Europe with openTEPES.		
WP5	Regarding Task 5.1, Dr Mittal mentioned that CICERO has shared some surveys with the consortium. She stated that there are different ways to understand the gaps in scenario representation. Lastly, she mentioned that discussions with WP2 teams are already taking place, and that although other tasks have not started yet coordination with the stakeholder engagement process will be a crucial part of initial activities.		
WP6	Next, Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) informed the consortium that HOLISTIC is focusing on preparing the technical report for WP6 and the work on the I ² AM PARIS platform, stating that there are no significant updates.		
WP7	Then, Dr Nikas encouraged partners to submit their work at the ECEMP conference, with a submission deadline on the 1 st of July. Dr Mittal and Dr Xexakis discussed the creation and/or enhancement of workspaces or applications in the platform regarding Task 5.1. Lastly, Dr Nikas thanked all partners for participating in this meeting.		

3.6 Executive Board Meeting – 16 October 2024

3.6.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Wednesday, 16 October 2024
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - Final stages of monitoring for RP1: Re-submission of interim report
 - Discussions during Interim review meeting & official (written) assessment
 - IAMC & ECEMP participation
 - WP2: Codesing
 - High-level Results of the Requirements Workshop
 - Lessons learnt from the organisation of the Requirements Workshop
 - Planning for the upcoming Foresight Workshops
 - Preparations for MS7 (Organisation of Workshops)
 - Plan for a multistakeholder workshop to finalise the research questions with WP5
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - Progress towards D3.2 (Model Development Strategy – Update):
 - Updates from MS5
 - Integrating insights from the Requirements workshop
 - Overall progress in model development and short updates for all six core models:
 - OMNIA
 - CLEWs-EU
 - GCAM-Europe
 - NEMESIS-World
 - OPEN-PROM
 - GEMINI-E3 EU
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Planning for MS6 (ENGAGE and MAgPIE*)
 - Progress on WP4 modules/tasks:
 - Labour, finance, well-being
 - Behavioural surveys
 - Circular economy
 - Climate/physical impacts
 - WP5: Apply & Explore
 - Updates on Task 5.1 & the preparation of the novel scenario space
 - Initial Plans for D5.1 (novel scenario space)
 - WP6: Open
 - Preparation and first plan on the organisation of thematic workshops
 - Updates on the I²AM PARIS platform
 - WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - Status update on D7.5 (Outreach)
 - Newsletters

- Social media

2. Any other business

3.6.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
4	Christina Tigka	ICCS
5	Anastasis Giannousakis	ICCS
6	Ioannis Tolios	ICCS
7	Claudia Rodes	BC3
8	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
9	Russell Horowitz	BC3
10	Shivika Mittal	CICERO
11	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
12	Tomasso Pilon	E4SMA
13	Sonja Sechi	E4SMA
14	Maurizio Gargiulo	E4SMA
15	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
16	Sara Lumbreras	COMILLAS
17	Luis Olmos Camacho	COMILLAS
18	Maria del Socorro Gómez Pérez	COMILLAS
19	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
20	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
21	Mark Sanders	UM
22	Marie Pied	ESMIA
23	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
24	Marc Vielle	EPFL
25	Mart van der Kam	UNIBAS
26	Vignesh Sridharan	Imperial
27	Maro Malliaroudaki	Imperial
28	Adam Hawkes	Imperial
29	Alvaro Calzadilla	UCL

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	Dr. Nikas (ICCS) opened the meeting by welcoming participants and introducing Dr. Mart van der Kam (UNIBAS), who briefly presented himself. He then updated the consortium on the EC's assessment, noting that the review was very positive—no deliverables need revision, with the evaluation featuring suggestions for future work. He also discussed financial aspects related to the 2 nd installment of	Revise financial aspects of the technical report	ICCS, all partners

	<p>payments. Dr. Mittal (CICERO) suggested incorporating a section in the next report on how EC recommendations were addressed. Dr. Nikas agreed and proposed including comments and responses, as done in similar projects. He congratulated everyone on their contributions and shared outreach updates, including two accepted DIAMOND papers at the ECMP conference. He encouraged partners to notify the ICCS team about any upcoming IAMC submissions or physical attendance.</p>		
WP2	<p>Mr. Cassolà (ISINNOVA) updated the consortium on WP2, noting that the Requirements Workshop report is nearly complete and encouraging modelling teams to integrate stakeholder insights into their work and the Model Development Strategy report. He shared that a post-workshop survey received moderate ratings, with feedback indicating potential improvements to stakeholder engagement. He mentioned that a draft format for the second workshop was shared and will be discussed further on a dedicated meeting this week. Dr. Sechi (E4SMA) suggested improving industry and water sector participation. Mr. Cassolà noted that some invited stakeholders did not attend and proposed expanding the stakeholder database. Dr. Nikas discussed on ways and aspirations to structure the second workshop to increase impact. Dr. Mittal (CICERO) announced plans for a WP5 multi-stakeholder workshop and proposed a bilateral meeting with ISINNOVA. She and Prof. Hawkes (Imperial) encouraged WP3 and WP4 task leaders to provide input.</p>	<p>Finalise the Requirement Workshop report.</p> <p>Plan the 2nd Workshop.</p> <p>Organise a multi-stakeholder workshop for WP5.</p>	<p>ISINNOVA</p> <p>ISINNOVA</p> <p>CICERO, Imperial, ISINNOVA</p>
WP3	<p>Next, Dr Sechi and Dr Dirk-Jan van de Ven (BC3) informed the consortium that a draft for Deliverable 3.2 will be shared in early November. In this context, Dr Koasidis replied that the plan seems good and he also suggested that the deliverable can build on top of MS5. He also mentioned that incorporating insight from the Requirements Workshop into Deliverable 3.2 is very important at this stage. Mr Cassolà mentioned that the Requirements Workshop report will be shared by the following Friday.</p> <p>Next, Dr Sechi briefed the partners on the updates done on each of the 6 core models and on upcoming bilateral meetings. In the same context.</p>	<p>Finalise the draft of Deliverable 3.2</p>	<p>E4SMA, BC3</p>
WP4	<p>Next, Dr Maro Malliaroudaki (Imperial) summarised the work done on ENGAGE and MAgPIE as part of MS7. In addition, she briefed the consortium on the progress made in steel, aluminium and cement modelling in Task 4.1. Moreover, she mentioned that a meeting with IIASA is planned regarding Task 4.2 and she also presented the recent work on the MAgPIE model. regarding Task 4.4, Dr Mittal informed the partners that a paper is planned to be prepared by the end of 2024 and then she summarised the progress made on METEOR. Then, Dr Malliaroudaki took the floor once again to</p>	<p>Paper on literature review on IAM development for labour, finance and demand,</p>	<p>UM</p>

	<p>present the work done in Task 4.5. She mentioned that a paper incorporating the literature review for labour, demand and finance IAM development is being prepared. Moreover, she mentioned that a theoretical model is almost complete and that a series of additional papers on model extensions will be prepared. In this context, Prof Mark Sanders (UM) further informed the consortium of these developments. Lastly, Dr Malliaroudaki, regarding Tasks 4.6 and 4.7 informed the consortium on the data retrieved from CLEWs-EU and the progress made on electricity modelling.</p>		
WP5	<p>Regarding WP5, Dr Mittal informed the consortium that the first deliverable of this WP has started being developed. She also mentioned that CICERO aims to add some harmonisation and land-use aspects in this work, stressing the importance of linkages with WP2. In this context, Dr Nikas suggested a meeting between ICCS, CICERO and ETH be organised to discuss the questions for the WP5 workshop.</p>	<p>Work on deliverable 5.1</p> <p>Organise a meeting for the WP5 workshop.</p>	<p>CICERO</p> <p>CICERO, ICCS, ETH</p>
WP6	<p>Regarding WP6, Dr Koasidis mentioned that the consortium needs to make some changes to the project's website to respond to the reviewers' recommendations. In this context, he also informed the partners that work on tools is also underway. Lastly, he mentioned that Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) and Dr Stephanie Briers (ETH) are discussing organising a webinar on transdisciplinarity. Furthermore, Dr Xexakis highlighted updates performed on the I²AM PARIS platform.</p>	<p>Changes on the project's website</p> <p>Organise a webinar on inclusivity.</p>	<p>HOLISTIC</p> <p>HOLISTIC, ETH</p>
WP7	<p>Regarding, WP7 he requested that partners inform the project's administration team of their participation in upcoming conferences. Lastly, Dr Nikas mentioned that the reviewers had no comment on the project's progress regarding its KPIs and thanked all participants for attending this meeting.</p>		

3.7 Executive Board Meeting – 4 December 2024

3.7.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Wednesday, 4 December 2024
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - Updates on final stages of monitoring for RP1: Re-submission of interim report
 - Scheduling the next General Assembly
 - Updates on IAMC participation & EGU session announcement
 - WP2: Codesing
 - Insights from the First Foresight Workshop
 - Submission of MS7 (Organisation of Workshops)
 - Preparation for the Second Foresight Workshop
 - Progress on preparations for the kick-off meeting of the multistakeholder discussion groups
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - Submission of D3.2 (Model Development Strategy – Update):
 - Overall progress in model development and short updates for all six core models:
 - OMNIA
 - CLEWs-EU
 - GCAM-Europe
 - NEMESIS-World
 - OPEN-PROM
 - GEMINI-E3 EU
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Planning for MS6 (ENGAGE and MAgPIE*)
 - Progress on WP4 modules/tasks:
 - Labour, finance, well-being
 - Behavioural surveys
 - Circular economy
 - Climate/physical impacts
 - WP5: Apply & Explore
 - Updates on Task 5.1 & the preparation of the novel scenario space
 - Initial plans for D5.1 (novel scenario space)
 - Launch of Tasks 5.3, 5.5, 5.6
 - WP6: Open
 - Preparation and first plan on the organisation of thematic workshops: Timeline
 - Updates on the I2AM PARIS platform
 - WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - Status update on D7.5 (Outreach)
 - Newsletters

- o Social media

2. Any other business

3.7.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
2	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
3	Christina Tigka	ICCS
4	Anastasis Giannousakis	ICCS
5	Ioannis Tolios	ICCS
6	Jon Sampedr	BC3
7	Claudia Rodes	BC3
8	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
9	Russell Horowitz	BC3
10	Kurt Kratena	CESAR
11	Shivika Mittal	CICERO
12	Tomasso Pilon	E4SMA
13	Sonja Sechi	E4SMA
14	Alessia Elia	E4SMA
15	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
16	Maria del Socorro Gómez Pérez	COMILLAS
17	Sara Lumbreras	COMILLAS
18	Luis Olmos Camacho	COMILLAS
19	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
20	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
21	Mark Sanders	UM
22	Tania Treibich	UM
23	Marie Pied	ESMIA
24	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
25	Marc Vielle	EPFL
26	Stephanie Briers	ETH
27	Lukas Engel	UNIBAS
28	Leigh Martindale	Imperial
29	Maro Malliaroudaki	Imperial

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	Dr Konstantinos Koasidis (ICCS) welcomed the consortium and informed partners that the interim report had been submitted, including all necessary justifications. He noted that there has been no communication from the European Commission since late November and that the timeline for the next payment remains unclear. He then announced that the next General Assembly (GA) meeting will be held online	Organise the next GA meeting	ICCS
		Roll out a Doodle for the summer GA	ICCS

	<p>in January, with a Doodle poll to follow to finalise the date, aiming to avoid conflicts with other events. He also shared that CICERO has offered to host the next physical GA meeting in Oslo in June and has proposed a few possible dates. A second Doodle poll will be launched so partners can indicate their availability. In this context, Dr Shivika Mittal (CICERO) asked partners to clarify whether their attendance will be tentative, as CICERO needs a rough headcount to book an appropriate venue. Finally, Dr Koasidis noted that the IAMC conference has concluded and expressed appreciation for seeing partners there. He also announced that a session at EGU 2025 will be hosted by Dr Jon Sampedro (BC3) and Dr Mittal, encouraging those interested to reach out for further information.</p>		
WP2	<p>Next, Mr Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) presented updates on WP2, highlighting insights from the Scenarios Workshop held in mid-November. He noted the use of a poll and a Miro Board for stakeholder engagement and informed partners that the first two workshops are reported in MS6 and are available on SharePoint. He added that feedback is being integrated and that a third workshop is planned using the same 3 Horizons Methodology. He also mentioned preparations for updating the stakeholder strategy in April and a meeting with ICCS and UNIBAS to explore broader citizen involvement.</p> <p>Dr Stephanie Briers (ETH) then shared updates on WP2–WP5 collaboration. She announced a stakeholder meeting scheduled for 14 January, with 30 external stakeholders already contacted. The webinar will serve as an introduction to the project’s process, followed by themed workshops with smaller groups. A preparatory partner meeting will be held early January, and she urged partners to respond promptly to emails. Dr Koasidis and Dr Briers discussed attendance limits, noting that no more than 11 consortium members should join to ensure balance. Dr Mittal and Dr Briers also discussed ways to keep non-attendees engaged, with ETH tracking interest for future involvement. Finally, Dr Briers pointed out that most participants are new to the stakeholder database, and Dr Koasidis noted the importance of not overburdening stakeholders with overlapping events.</p>	<p>Prepare the 3rd Stakeholder engagement workshop</p> <p>Organise a meeting with ICCS and UNIBAS on stakeholder engagement</p> <p>Organise a stakeholder kick-off webinar and 3 following thematical workshops</p> <p>Organise a consortium meeting to prepare the needed presentations.</p>	<p>ISINNOVA</p> <p>ISINNOVA, ICCS, UNIBAS</p> <p>ETH</p> <p>ETH, all partners</p>
WP3	<p>Then, Dr Sonja Sechi (E4SMA) informed the consortium that all models are progressing smoothly and summarised the developments on each of the 6 core models.</p> <p>Next, Dr Dirk-Jan van de Ven (BC3) informed the partners that D3.2 was finished the previous week and thanked all teams for contributing. He also mentioned that BC3 is collecting data and feedback on harmonization, although using may depend on whether the project intends to prepare some intercomparison studies. In this context, Dr Koasidis stated that D3.2 was a result of very nice work and he summarised</p>		

	<p>its contents, also stressing that there is a very demanding deadline to incorporate stakeholder feedback from the workshops held so far.</p>		
WP4	<p>Afterwards, Dr Maro Malliaroudaki (Imperial) briefed the consortium on the upcoming MS7 for January 2025 on MAgPIE and ENGAGE, mentioning that a meeting between Imperial, Oxford, UCL and CICERO partners will take place. Next, she presented the progress done on each Task focusing on related modelling aspects and interlinkages as well as relevant papers under preparation. Next, Dr Mittal, Dr Malliaroudaki and Dr Anastasis Giannousakis (ICCS) discussed issues regarding the MAgPIE emulator, with the latter mentioning that there is already one, which is open-source and used in the REMIND model. In this context, Dr Mittal commented on the differences between the emulators used for MESSAGE and REMIND. Next, Dr Koasidis suggested that these issues can be further discussed at the related meeting on Friday. He also informed the partners that Prof Michael Obersteiner (Oxford) has sent an e-mail containing relevant information.</p> <p>Then, Dr Kurt Kratena (CESAR) commented on household data, stating that his team now has a clear plan on how to combine survey results. He also mentioned that there are discussions with modelling teams on providing data that meet the models’ requirements. He also noted that there is an issue with the WILIAM database and the income categories. Lastly, he mentioned that a 2nd data delivery will be prepared for modelling teams, which will include more data on heterogeneity.</p>	<p>Meeting for MS7</p> <p>2nd data delivery on heterogeneity</p>	<p>Imperial, Oxford, UCL, CICERO</p> <p>CESAR</p>
WP5	<p>Next, Dr Mittal informed the partners that 60-70% of the writing of D5.1 is completed and that the relevant paper is in a similar phase. She mentioned that CICERO is also working with stakeholders on research questions. In this context, Dr Koasidis and Dr Mittal had a discussion on how to incorporate the insights from the first two, with Dr Mittal mentioning that CICERO intends to do that after the Christmas holidays.</p>	<p>Prepare D5.1 and the relevant paper</p> <p>Incorporate stakeholder insights from the first two workshops</p>	<p>CICERO</p> <p>CICERO</p>
WP6	<p>Afterwards, Dr Koasidis presented immediate actions related to WP6, focusing on the deliverable of synergies with communities of practice. He mentioned that ICCS and HOLISTIC will share a draft version of the deliverable with partners so they can add their input if necessary for specific communities of each model.</p> <p>Then, Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) informed the consortium that the vetting platform is almost ready and is currently at a testing stage. He added that news on the platform’s release will come soon and that HOLISTIC will also share some manuals and organise relevant webinars. Moreover, he mentioned that some thematic webinars will be organised, for which initial material is already prepared. He also stated</p>	<p>Create a deliverable on synergies with communities of practice</p> <p>Finalise the vetting platform and organise relevant webinars</p>	<p>ICCS, HOLISTIC, all partners.</p> <p>HOLISTIC</p>

	that it may be to avoid organising those during January since the project will be hosting two stakeholder workshops. Moreover, he suggested that a meeting with other partners be organised to discuss the relevant paper. In this context, Dr Mittal and Dr Xexakis discussed when to submit the paper, stressing the importance of publishing as soon as possible so the IPCC can take the project’s processes into consideration.		
WP7	Next, on WP7, Dr Koasidis informed the consortium that D7.5 was submitted on time. In addition, he added that the consortium is doing its best communication-wise, trying to increase engagement on LinkedIn. Then, Dr Koasidis mentioned that newsletters are being shared and that one more will be shared before Christmas.	Prepare the December newsletter	HOLISTIC
	Lastly, he thanked everybody for joining the meeting.		

3.8 General Assembly Meeting (29 January 2025)

The 4th General Assembly meeting of the project took place on the 29th of January online via Microsoft Teams. It aimed to discuss the project's latest developments, focusing on the 6 core models as well as future stakeholder engagement activities. In this meeting, all partners were represented with at least one colleague. Moreover, there was an SAB session in which some SAB members participated.

3.8.1 Agenda

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Wednesday, January 29, 2025, online (all times in CET)			
09:00 – 09:05	I.1	Get together	ICCS
09:05 – 09:30	I.2	WP1 – Manage & Coordinate <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination & management • Progress so far • 2025 deliverables & milestones • Feedback from the interim review meeting • General Assembly (Oslo, June 2025) 	ICCS
09:30 – 10:30	I.3	WP2 – Codesign <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflections on foresight workshops • Planning for the final foresight workshop with stakeholders and follow-up foresights with citizens • Multi-stakeholder discussion groups – next steps • Actionable items from stakeholder engagement 	ISINNOVA & ETH
10:30 – 10:45	Coffee Break		
10:45 – 12:00	I.4	WP3 – Update & Upgrade <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progress towards the release of first stable versions • Brief presentation of current versions, stakeholder impact on development strategy (per IAM) • Data harmonisation: sources, high-level assumptions 	E4SMA & BC3
12:00 – 13:00	I.5	WP4 – Integrate & Expand <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progress in and current version (per module) • Implementation of plans for linking with core IAMs 	Imperial
13:00 – 13:45	Lunch Break		
13:45-14:45	I.6	Scientific Advisory Board Welcome remarks, project progress/planning, feedback	SAB, ICCS, All partners
14:45 – 16:00	I.7	WP5 – Apply & Explore <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Novel scenario space and project scenario design • From development to use: Shedding light on the new capacities (per activity) • Multi-stakeholder discussion groups: expectations 	CICERO
16:00 – 16:15	Coffee Break		
16:15 – 16:40	I.8	WP6 – Open <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I²AM PARIS: progress and application library • Plan for the implementation of thematic webinars • Dev guidelines: standard & IAM dev practices • Generalisation of vetting and validation processes Communities of practice: requirements	ICCS & HOLISTIC

16:45 – 17:00	I.9	WP7 – Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ideas for boosting our visual identity Progress with regard to CDE planning & KPIs	HOLISTIC
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3.8.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Kimon Georgiou	ICCS
4	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
5	Stratis Alexandrou	ICCS
6	Anastasis Giannousakis	ICCS
7	Dirk-Jan Van de Ven	BC3
8	Jon Sampedro	BC3
9	Claudia Rodes	BC3
10	Russell Horowitz	BC3
11	Kurt Kratena	CESAR
12	Shivika Mittal	CICERO
13	Glen Peters	CICERO
14	Ben Sanderson	CICERO
15	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
16	Karstein Maseide	CICERO
17	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
18	Marios Karmellos	CYI
19	Tomasso Pilon	E4SMA
20	Alessia Elia	E4SMA
21	Maurizio Gargiulo	E4SMA
22	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
23	Stefanos Tsotras	HOLISTIC
24	Angelos Potiriadis	HOLISTIC
25	Christos Petkidis	HOLISTIC
26	María del Socorro Gómez Pérez	COMILLAS
27	Sara Lumbreras	COMILLAS
28	Andrés Ramos Galán	COMILLAS
29	Carlo Sessa	ISINNOVA
30	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
31	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
32	Paul Zagamé	SEURECO
33	Hayat Mekki	SEURECO
34	Eoghan O'Connell	UM
35	Mark Sanders	UM
36	Tania Treibich	UM
37	Prescott Morley	UM
38	Sascha Serebriakova	UM
39	Marie Pied	ESMIA
40	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
41	Marc Vielle	EPFL
42	Bianca Vienni-Baptista	ETH
43	Stephanie Briers	ETH
44	Lukas Engel	UNIBAS

45	Mart van der Kam	UNIBAS
46	Maro Malliaroudaki	Imperial
47	Leigh Martindale	Imperial
48	Michael Obersteiner	Oxford
49	Alvaro Calzadilla	UCL
50	Dan Zhang	UCL
51	Pietro Lubello	UCL
52	Steve Pye	UCL
53	Jessica Jewel	SAB
54	Lukas Hermwill	SAB
55	David McCollum	SAB
56	Stephanie Waldhoff	SAB

Minutes: Main issues discussed			
Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
Welcome	Dr Konstantinos Koasidis (ICCS) greeted the consortium and thanked everyone for attending.		
WP1	<p>Dr. Koasidis (ICCS) presented an overview of WP1, highlighting a Gantt chart for the next six months and confirming that the first reporting period concluded successfully. He summarised key points from the technical and financial reports and shared feedback from the Project Officer on harmonisation, submission timelines, publication strategy, and innovation. A figure showing PM allocation across WPs and partners was also shown, with a reminder for partners to verify their recorded work effort.</p> <p>For Task 1.2, he outlined the deliverables and milestones submitted in the past six months and flagged a demanding upcoming period (10 deliverables and 10 milestones due by July). The next GA meeting will be held in Oslo on June 12–13, hosted by CICERO, aligning with the nearby EAERE conference, which the Project Officer strongly encouraged partners to attend.</p> <p>He also shared feedback from SAB members at the last GA, mainly regarding COP participation and modelling. A longer-term Gantt chart through M36 was presented, summarising WP requirements. Finally, Dr. Nikas urged partners to submit to EAERE before the January 31 deadline, echoing the Project Officer’s recommendation.</p>	Organise the next GA meeting	CICERO
WP2	<p>Mr Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) opened the session with a summary of insights from the Requirements and 1st Foresight workshops, which will feed into MS6. He presented a 3 Horizons framework, focusing on Horizon 2 and previewed the foresight workshop, highlighting its multi-stakeholder format, links with WP5, and alternative scenarios. He also shared a proposed timeline.</p> <p>Mr Carlo Sessa (ISINNOVA) followed with details on the</p>	<p>Organise the 2nd Foresight workshop and the Ethical workshop for citizens</p> <p>Organise the 3 multi-stakeholder</p>	<p>ISINNOVA, ETH</p> <p>ETH</p>

	<p>Ethical Citizens’ Workshop, planned after the 2nd Foresight session, explaining the approach and challenges. Citizen assemblies will begin in Milan and potentially extend to other cities. Dr Stephanie Briers (ETH) proposed a bilateral meeting with ISINNOVA to align efforts and ensure timely inputs for D2.3. Mr Sessa suggested workshops could occur in June or September to fit the deadline. Mr Cassolà supported collaboration between ISINNOVA, ETH, and CICERO to better integrate WP5 aspects and engage CDR-related stakeholders.</p> <p>Dr Bianca Vienni-Baptista (ETH) emphasised the importance of incorporating EC feedback and stakeholder selection. She and Mr Sessa discussed better coordination of stakeholder processes, with Dr Glen Peters (CICERO) cautioning about timing for modelling input, with Mr Sessa reiterating alignment with WP5 as the priority.</p> <p>Dr Briers then presented the structure of the ETH-led kick-off webinar, outlining stakeholder group compositions and co-creation processes for research questions. She shared the webinar schedule (Feb 18–27), plans for group reports, and logistical details. Feedback from the webinar was also reviewed. Dr Mittal (CICERO), Dr Peters, and Dr Briers discussed the need to adapt group meetings based on the first session’s outcome. Dr Nikas flagged potential overlaps with the foresight workshop; Dr Briers responded that ETH’s stakeholder pool is distinct.</p> <p>Further coordination discussions included a WP6 reporting exchange between Dr Xexakis (HOLISTIC) and ETH colleagues, with Mr Cassolà confirming ISINNOVA will provide internal reports. Dr Mittal raised the need to prioritise research questions based on modelling capacity, with WP3 involvement. Dr Vienni-Baptista noted that not all questions can necessarily be modelled, and Dr Briers added that some could be future research topics. Feedback from the CLEWs team was welcomed—Dr Taliotis (CYI) confirmed their support. The session closed with Dr Nikas and Dr Mittal addressing timing and coordination across activities.</p>	<p>group meetings</p>	
<p>WP3</p>	<p>Dr Dirk-Jan van de Ven (BC3) opened the modelling session by outlining key progress on WP3, including submitted deliverables and milestones, and turned attention to the upcoming MS8. He presented the Model Harmonisation Protocol, stressing the importance of aligning key parameters across models while allowing flexibility depending on geographic coverage and model structure. He clarified that harmonisation efforts won’t constrain scenario development, as input diversity can still reflect alternative narratives. This led to a brief exchange with Drs Mittal, Peters, and Vielle on the use of multiple baseline scenarios, especially across different SSPs.</p> <p>The session moved into model-specific updates, with Dr van</p>	<p>Deliver MS8 by July</p> <p>Deliver the final version of GCAM Europe by June 2026</p> <p>Deliver the first stable version of OMNIA by July 2025</p>	<p>BC3</p> <p>BC3</p> <p>E4SMA</p>

	<p>de Ven presenting the GCAM-Europe developments, including regional granularity, trade flows, and stakeholder-informed revisions in various sectors. He also noted the documentation timeline for the model's versions and provided example outputs.</p> <p>Dr Alessia Elia (E4SMA) then introduced the OMNIA model timeline, highlighting improvements in spatial and sectoral detail, guided by stakeholder feedback. She noted soft-linking efforts with other models and reported on updates using VEDA templates, as well as adjustments to energy service demand assumptions.</p> <p>Dr Constantinos Taliotis (CYI) followed with updates on the CLEWs-EU model, announcing that the aggregated version is live and the disaggregated one is planned by M36. He emphasised how behavioural and technological aspects raised by stakeholders have been reflected in the model, particularly regarding CCS and land-water interactions.</p> <p>Next, Dr Sigit Perdana (EPFL) presented progress on GEMINE-E3 EU, noting its developments on air pollutants, hydrogen use, and macroeconomic dynamics such as labour and household heterogeneity. He shared how stakeholder insights have informed the modelling of sectoral interactions and system-wide impacts.</p> <p>Dr Baptiste Boitier (SEURECO) shifted the focus to NEMESIS-World, noting that much of the upcoming work will take place in 2025. He provided an overview of the current focus on behavioural equations, economic data, and employment effects, linking these with stakeholder feedback on finance, behaviour, and heterogeneity.</p> <p>Dr Anastasis Giannousakis (ICCS) closed the model updates with a presentation on OPEN-PROM, highlighting improvements in temporal resolution, open-source toolchains, and its integration with other models like MAgPIE and openTEPES. He also outlined progress toward MS8 and discussed open data processes, prompting Dr Boitier to suggest a call on the utility of the mrprom library.</p> <p>Throughout the session, cross-cutting coordination remained a consistent theme, with repeated emphasis on soft-linking models, maintaining transparent documentation, and using stakeholder input not only to improve model detail but also to drive convergence across WP3.</p>	<p>Deliver the disaggregated version of CLEWs-EU by November 2025</p>	<p>CYI, Imperial, ICCS,</p>
<p>WP4</p>	<p>Dr Maro Malliaroudaki (Imperial) presented the WP4 timeline with a clear illustration of how its tasks connect to WP3 models, also noting the upcoming submission of Deliverables D4.1 and D4.2. She provided a task-by-task progress update, with emphasis on model linkages, and specifically outlined developments in Task 4.1 related to the ENGAGE model.</p> <p>Dr Mittal then presented updates on the MAgPIE model, highlighting the incorporation of harmonised socioeconomic drivers, an update to integrate recent national pledges, and</p>	<p>Deliver D4.1 and D4.2 by June and July</p>	<p>Imperial</p>

	<p>the development of an R script for exporting MAgPIE outputs to OMNIA. She confirmed that the MS7 report documenting the soft-linking between MAgPIE and OMNIA has been almost ready and outlined the next steps under Task 4.2, including AFOLU harmonisation, data feeding to WP5, and ongoing refinements to MAgPIE.</p> <p>Dr Kurt Kratena (CESAR) followed with an overview of CESAR’s contributions, including coordination with WP3 teams and the new household heterogeneity workplan agreed with BC3. He described the dataset being developed, focusing on household income, consumption patterns, and data typology, and summarised how this data is being progressively integrated into WP3 models.</p> <p>Dr Ben Sanderson (CICERO) then briefed the group on progress with OpenSCM and METEOR. He mentioned an upcoming paper and a submission to the EGU conference, and presented a schematic showing how METEOR functions. He also discussed efforts underway to connect METEOR outputs with WP3 models.</p> <p>Prof Mark Sanders provided a short update on Task 4.5, focusing on the literature review, the development of theoretical and agent-based models, and recent paper submissions.</p> <p>Mr Lukas Engel (UNIBAS) presented on Task 4.6, detailing progress on the behavioural module for OMNIA, GCAM-Europe, and CLEWs-EU. He explained the current structure across micro, meso, and macro levels, supported by a visual, and discussed ongoing data collection, particularly regarding electric vehicles and psychological factors influencing behaviour.</p> <p>Ms Maria del Socorro Gomez Perez (COMILLAS) then showcased progress on OpenTEPES and its integration with GCAM-Europe, outlining the three-step implementation process. She presented data inputs, regional coverage, and modelled connections, along with hourly energy demand and dispatch graphics which will inform GCAM. This prompted a broader discussion on soft-linking, with Dr Nikas calling for a consolidated timeline, and Dr Malliaroudaki committing to urge all teams to coordinate accordingly. Dr Koasidis reinforced that full model interlinking remains a core obligation under the Grant Agreement.</p>		
SAB Session	<p>Following the lunch break, the SAB session commenced with Dr Nikas greeting the SAB members, and informing them about the location of the next GA meeting. Then, he presented the progress of the project since May focusing on the positive feedback from the project officer, the project’s key outputs, the intensive stakeholder engagement activity, the model development progress and the timeline of the next 6-month period.</p> <p>Afterwards, an SAB member, Dr Nikas, Dr Vienni-Baptista and</p>		

	<p>Dr Briers had a discussion on sharing workshop insights with the general public as well as on the project’s options for increasing its social outreach via COP events and its website. Next, another SAB member made a point about examining dystopian scenarios with Dr Mittal and Dr Peters joining the conversation. Moreover, SAB members mentioned options in this direction, with Dr Nikas replying that the consortium is interested in scoping potential to pursue these recommendations. Additionally, he added that the consortium partners are already involved (e.g., through synergistic publications) in this endeavour.</p> <p>In conclusion, Dr Nikas mentioned that the SAB will be informed about the insights of this SAB session and thanked all attending SAB members for their participation and insightful suggestions.</p>		
<p>WP5</p>	<p>Following the SAB session, Dr Glen Peters provided an overview of the WP5 agenda, reiterating its objectives, timeline, and tasks. He confirmed that Deliverable D5.1 is ready for submission, with a follow-up update planned for Month 42. He outlined the structure of D5.1 and noted that it will serve as the basis for forthcoming publications. Dr Peters presented a schematic of scenario pipeline uncertainties and shared data visualisations covering scenario distributions by model and energy demand. Emphasising the need to tailor scenario assessments to specific research questions, he cautioned against over-relying on aggregate statistics. He also discussed efforts in data harmonisation and vetting, showcasing figures related to IPCC scenarios, CO₂ reduction, and carbon budgets. He concluded this segment by illustrating the scenario space—qualitative and quantitative—using SSPs as a reference point. Prof Michael Obersteiner (Oxford) then presented the status of Task 5.2, focusing on the integration of human systems, biophysical impacts, and uncertainties under transient climate conditions. He introduced the modelling of human diseases within MAGPIE and IAMs, discussing links between health outcomes and variables like food prices, air pollution, and climate impacts. He showed preliminary MAGPIE results on BMI distribution and a diagram outlining potential soft linkages with macroeconomic modules. A brief discussion with Dr Mittal followed regarding the food demand model.</p> <p>Dr Maro Malliaroudaki summarised the launch of Task 5.3, outlining its objectives, structure, and timeline. She presented a Gantt chart tracking progress and highlighted early activities, including the disruptive events plenary, a stakeholder workshop, and a literature review. Dr Mittal then shared details of a paper under development on Solar Radiation Management (SRM) in climate scenario frameworks. A broader discussion followed between Dr Mittal, Dr Malliaroudaki, Prof Obersteiner, and Dr Peters on</p>	<p>Submit D5.1</p> <p>Submit 2 papers related to D5.1</p> <p>SDG mapping in models by June</p> <p>Organise a WP5 meeting on multi-stakeholder discussion groups</p>	<p>CICERO</p> <p>CICERO</p> <p>ICCS</p> <p>CICERO</p>

	<p>how the consortium defines “disruptive events” and which specific events are currently in focus.</p> <p>In a separate presentation, Prof Alvaro Calzadilla (UCL) introduced the ENGAGE material model, highlighting sectoral classifications and referencing an alternative dataset. He also shared upcoming simulation plans, showing how OMNIA and ENGAGE will be soft-linked across baseline, policy, and circular economy scenarios. He concluded by summarising the current status and next steps.</p> <p>Prof Mark Sanders reported on Task 5.4, using a schematic to position the task within the broader modelling framework. He reviewed progress across three themes: finance, labour, and household heterogeneity, indicating what has been accomplished and what still needs to be done.</p> <p>Dr Mart van der Kam (UNIBAS) followed with insights into the human behaviour component, presenting a case study, outlining the methodological approach, and inviting input from partners.</p> <p>Dr Koasidis then introduced the timeline and structure for Task 5.5, detailing upcoming deliverables and milestones. He explained that ICCS plans to start SDG mappings across models by June, followed by targeted surveys to enhance modelling of SDG-related dynamics. He noted particular focus on biodiversity, labour, and the water cycle, and mentioned growing interest in SDG16 (peace, justice, and strong institutions).</p> <p>Dr Peters concluded with a summary of the multi-stakeholder discussion group objectives and timeline, proposing that CICERO convene a dedicated WP5 meeting. This led to a broader exchange involving Dr Nikas, Dr Mittal, and Dr Peters on defining the number and scope of model runs and research questions. Dr Vienni-Baptista suggested collecting stakeholder questions and adjusting them for practical integration, noting the importance of careful translation and framing. Dr Koasidis acknowledged the potential workload implications of diverging stakeholder inputs, while Dr Vienni-Baptista stressed the importance of semantics and methodological alignment. Mr Cassolà (ISINNOVA) offered to facilitate further discussions, and Dr Peters and Dr Briers considered how to streamline coordination between WP2 and WP5. Dr Vienni-Baptista concluded by recommending small improvements to enhance collaboration, and Dr Mittal requested that key points and expectations be summarised and shared via email.</p>		
<p>WP6</p>	<p>Dr Koasidis then presented the timeline, milestones, and deliverables for WP6, noting that the second update of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is expected by November. He introduced an illustration of the Open Science Protocol, and upcoming development of supporting guidelines. He also outlined synergies with other projects and the consortium’s</p>	<p>Prepare the 2nd update of the DMP by November</p> <p>Develop</p>	<p>ICCS, HOLISTIC</p> <p>ICCS, HOLISTIC</p>

	<p>engagement in communities of practice, with particular reference to the MAIA Multiply Program. Additionally, he reported that D6.4 has been submitted, highlighting project activities, webinars, and exchanges on sustainability, with an update scheduled for Month 36. He noted the project officer’s emphasis on clearly defining each project’s contribution.</p> <p>Following this, Dr Xexakis introduced the MAIA project, announcing a series of upcoming webinars on stakeholder participation, lessons from AR5/AR6, and open development. He added that capacity-building activities—such as videos, webinars, and training sessions—will commence after July. Dr Xexakis also outlined development pipelines and presented selected principles. He noted that an analysis of best IAM development practices is in preparation and introduced the new I2AM PARIS platform. Lastly, he summarised the objectives of D6.8, focusing on the stakeholder-informed application library and the integration of LLM support for enhanced visualisation.</p>	<p>guidelines for the Open Science Protocol</p> <p>Organise core capacity development activities after July</p>	<p>HOLISTIC</p>
<p>WP7</p>	<p>Regarding WP7, Dr Xexakis summarised its timeline and deliverables and then proceeded to Task 7.1 which is related to the project’s visual identity. In this context, he mentioned everything is completed except infographics (e.g., model infographics), videos (e.g., model tutorials) and media articles.</p> <p>Regarding the project’s CDE plan (Task 7.2) he confirmed that everything is progressing smoothly.</p> <p>Lastly, regarding Task 7.3, he summarised the conferences in which the consortium will participate in 2025 and presented the CDE indicators of the project. In this context, he briefed the partners on the next steps regarding the project’s social media presence focusing on media and infographics as well as the issue of the evolution of X (ex-Twitter) and joining BlueSky.</p>		
	<p>In conclusion, Dr Nikas encouraged WP2 and WP5 partners to talk about the discussion groups and thanked everybody for participating in the meeting.</p>		

3.9 Executive Board Meeting – 26 March 2025

3.9.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Wednesday, 26 March 2025
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - Quality management process – Internal Reviewer Assignments for 2025
 - Scheduling the next General Assembly
 - Upcoming conferences
 - WP2: Codensing
 - Updates from the organisation of the first round of the multistakeholder discussion groups and next steps
 - Plan for D2.5 – Updated stakeholder-informed research questions
 - Preparation for the Second Foresight Workshop
 - Progress towards D2.3 – Updated stakeholder engagement strategy
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - Preparations for developing a strategy towards claiming MS8 (first version of the models)
 - Updates and further requirements on harmonisation
 - Overall progress in model development and short updates for all six core models:
 - OMNIA
 - CLEWs-EU
 - GCAM-Europe
 - NEMESIS-World
 - OPEN-PROM
 - GEMINI-E3 EU
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Progress on WP4 modules/tasks:
 - Labour, finance, well-being
 - Behavioural surveys
 - Circular economy
 - Climate/physical impacts
 - Land use, nature-based solutions
 - Household Heterogeneity
 - Electricity Module
 - WP5: Apply & Explore
 - Updates from the WP5 task leaders meeting.
 - Reflections on the feedback from the multi-stakeholder discussion groups:
 - Group 1: Climate change
 - Group 2: Climate action
 - Group 3: User driven scenarios
 - WP6: Open

- Reflections on the first thematic workshop and produced resource (video)
- Upcoming webinars
- Updates on the I2AM PARIS platform
- Plan towards D6.6 – Development Pipelines
- WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - Newsletters
 - Social media

2. Any other business

3.9.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
2	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
3	Christina Tigka	ICCS
4	Stratis Alexandrou	ICCS
5	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
6	Kimon Georgiou	ICCS
7	Anastasis Giannousakis	ICCS
8	Claudia Rodes	BC3
9	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
10	Russell Horowitz	BC3
11	Glen Peters	CICERO
12	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
13	Shivika Mittal	CICERO
14	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
15	Tomasso Pilon	E4SMA
16	Maurizio Gargiulo	E4SMA
17	Alessia Elia	E4SMA
18	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
19	Apostolos Tsotras	HOLISTIC
20	Maria del Socorro Gómez Pérez	COMILLAS
21	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
22	Paul Zagame	SEURECO
23	Hayat Mekki	SEURECO
24	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
25	Marie Pied	ESMIA
26	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
27	Marc Vielle	EPFL
28	Bianca Vienni-Baptista	ETH
29	Mart van der Kam	UNIBAS
30	Vignesh Sridharan	Imperial
31	Michael Obersteiner	Oxford
32	Steve Pye	UCL

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	<p>Dr Konstantinos Koasidis (ICCS) opened the meeting by welcoming participants and providing information on the Excel file related to General Assembly logistics and attendance. He then informed the consortium of a short meeting with the WorldTrans project, scheduled for the day before the GA, to test models and explore synergies. DIAMOND partners were encouraged to suggest models for testing. Dr Mittal (CICERO) and Dr Koasidis briefly discussed the expected participation of WorldTrans partners in this session. Dr Koasidis noted that an updated agenda would be shared after finalising the SAB session arrangements. He also informed the consortium that ICCS and SEURECO teams have been accepted to present at the EAERE conference, with Ms Hayat Mekki representing SEURECO. Dr Nikas (ICCS) highlighted the importance of meeting the project officer at the event. Finally, Dr Koasidis asked partners to express interest in reviewing upcoming deliverables.</p>	<p>Fill in the GA attendance file</p> <p>Indicate which deliverables to review</p>	<p>All partners</p> <p>All partners</p>
WP2	<p>Mr Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) presented the workshop report prepared, stating that the Scenarios workshops can be held later in 2025 to ensure coordination with the other engagement activities. He also noted that ISINNOVA is coordinating with Italian cities for the Ethical foresight, with Milan already confirmed and others, such as Bologna, showing interest. This workshop may take place either before summer or in September.</p> <p>Mr Cassolà and Dr Koasidis then discussed the timeline and insights of the Foresight workshops, considering how they align with ETH's collected research questions and ongoing WP5 activities. Dr Mittal also joined the discussion, reflecting on how the workshops have contributed to WP5.</p> <p>Next, Dr Bianca Vienni-Baptista (ETH) informed the consortium that ETH is organising the final stakeholder meeting the following week and will soon provide modellers with the derived research questions. She added that ETH plans to begin Phase 3 around June and suggested including a related session in the upcoming GA meeting.</p>	<p>Organise the Scenarios and Ethical workshops</p> <p>Host final stakeholder meetings</p>	<p>ISINNOVA</p> <p>ETH</p>
WP3	<p>Then, Dr Alessia Elia (E4SMA) mentioned that preparations for MS8 have started and stated that a template for each model will be shared with the consortium shortly. Moreover, Dr Koasidis mentioned that ICCS and HOLISTIC are working on a pipeline to release models by July that could be aligned and assist with the efforts for claiming MS8.</p> <p>Moreover, Dr Elia briefed the consortium on the progress of each of the project's 6 core models. Moreover, Dr Elia and Dr van de Ven informed the consortium of the updates on linkages with WP4 models (namely, ENGAGE, openTEPES and the work done by CESAR). Similarly, Dr Marc Vielle (EPFL) informed the meeting attendants on the meeting that EPFL</p>	<p>Share a table of contents for each model</p> <p>Prepare a model release pipeline</p>	<p>E4SMA</p> <p>ICCS, HOLISTIC</p>

	and UM partners had on labour aspects in GEMINI. Lastly, Dr Boitier mentioned that his team will communicate with UM partners on linking their model with the labour work.		
WP4	Regarding WP4, Dr Koasidis mentioned that there have been no significant updates since the previous GA meeting according to Imperial partners, while Prof Steve Pye (UCL) summarised the work done for the upcoming deliverable, stating that everything is on track.		
WP5	Next, Dr Glen Peters (CICERO) summarised items related to research questions deriving from WP2 and the stakeholder meetings, stating that the consortium can discuss who follows each research question during the upcoming GA meeting in Oslo. Then, he briefed the consortium on the progress of each Task of WP5, stating that everything is on track so far.		
WP6	Afterwards, Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) summarised the work done on publishing models online, mentioning that HOLISTIC will provide a relevant pipeline. Moreover, he said that HOLISITC will share a short survey on open source aspects, stating that one person per modelling team should answer it. Moreover, he mentioned that HOLISTIC is communicating with the CLEWs modelling team, for which a separate meeting will take place. Lastly, he briefed the consortium on a webinar that HOLISTIC hosted, which had a satisfactory attendance rate, with Dr Koasidis adding that the recording was uploaded and he recommended partners to disseminate it further. In this context, Dr Xexakis mentioned that a 2 nd webinar will be organised, aiming to include other partners as well as members from the SAB.	Share a brief survey on open source aspects	HOLISTIC, all partners
WP7	Regarding WP7, Dr Xexakis mentioned that there are no significant updates and informed once again the consortium of the WorldTrans meeting. He also requested that project partners inform HOLISTIC if they participate in any conferences. In this context, Dr Peters mentioned that the ISEE conference takes place in Oslo in June, but submissions have been closed. He also encouraged partners to participate in IPCC AR7 processes, focusing on Chapter 3.	Inform HOLISTIC on conference participation	All partners
	Lastly, Dr Koasidis thanked all participants and mentioned that the next EB meeting will take place after Easter.		

3.10 Executive Board Meeting – 30 April 2025

3.10.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting

Wednesday, 30 April 2025

14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - Updates on the organisation of the next General Assembly
 - Status of D1.3 – Report on project and SAB Meetings – Update 1
 - IAMC and ECEMP call for papers and deadlines
 - WP2: Codensing
 - Submission of D2.3 – Updated stakeholder engagement strategy
 - Updates on the organisation of the Second Foresight and Citizens' Workshops
 - Reflections from the multistakeholder discussion groups
 - Upcoming submission of D2.5 – Updated stakeholder-informed research questions
 - Conclusion of Phase 1 and next steps
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - Template on the technical drafts for MS8 (first version of the models)
 - Overall progress in model development and short updates for all six core models:
 - OMNIA
 - CLEWs-EU
 - GCAM-Europe
 - NEMESIS-World
 - OPEN-PROM
 - GEMINI-E3 EU
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Progress on WP4 modules/tasks:
 - Labour, finance, well-being
 - Behavioural surveys
 - Circular economy
 - Climate/physical impacts
 - Land use, nature-based solutions
 - Household Heterogeneity
 - Electricity Module
 - WP5: Apply & Explore
 - Final feedback from the multi-stakeholder discussion groups:
 - Group 1: Climate change
 - Group 2: Climate action
 - Group 3: User driven scenarios
 - WP6: Open
 - Survey on model development pipelines
 - Upcoming submission of D6.6 – Development Pipelines

- Progress on the organisation of the upcoming webinar on IPCC scenarios
- Updates on the I²AM PARIS platform
- WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - Newsletters
 - Social media

2. Any other business

3.10.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
2	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
3	Christina Tigka	ICCS
4	Stratis Alexandrou	ICCS
5	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
6	Kimon Georgiou	ICCS
7	Anastasis Giannousakis	ICCS
8	Claudia Rodes	BC3
9	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
10	Jon Sampedro	BC3
11	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
12	Tomasso Pilon	E4SMA
13	Maurizio Gargiulo	E4SMA
14	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
15	Maria del Socorro Gómez Pérez	COMILLAS
16	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
17	Hayat Mekki	SEURECO
18	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
19	Marie Pied	ESMIA
20	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
21	Marc Vielle	EPFL
22	Stephani Briers	ETH
23	Maro Malliaroudaki	Imperial
24	Vignesh Sridharan	Imperial

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	The meeting started with Dr Konstantinos Koasidis (ICCS) greeting all partners. Next, he briefed the consortium on the General Assembly meeting agenda, and particularly on the WP2 workshops. He also informed the meeting's participants of the planned meeting with the WorldTrans project team, the timeline of which is not yet finalised. The ICCS team will communicate with WorldTrans partners for further arrangements. Moreover, he briefed the consortium on the		

	<p>progress of D1.3 regarding the project's meetings and SAB sessions. Lastly, he reminded the partners of the IAMC and ECEMP conferences, encouraging them to submit their work, and stressing the importance of project work being presented in such fora.</p>		
WP2	<p>Mr Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) informed the consortium that the revised version of D2.3 is ready, with Dr Koasidis noting that ICCS is conducting final checks. Mr Cassolà then briefed partners on the workshops planned for the GA meeting in Oslo, following coordination with ETH.</p> <p>He also updated the consortium on preparations for the foresight workshops with citizens scheduled for September, noting progress with Bologna and Trento. He discussed aspects related to participant fatigue and suggested discussing the timing of future activities. Dr Koasidis responded that financial incentives may not be feasible but encouraged considering other approaches to increase participation.</p> <p>Next, Dr Stephanie Briers (ETH) reported on the discussion groups and noted that a summary report would soon be shared. The report will feature research questions and it will, incorporate both stakeholder and partner input.</p> <p>She then outlined the GA meeting workshops, during which final research questions will be selected based on feasibility and relevance. These will be coordinated between WP2 and WP5, and she urged all partners to provide input, as the outcome will impact all modelling work. Some of the selected questions will also feed into the foresight workshops. Dr Koasidis added that the deliverable on research questions is due in May and that many partners have already contributed.</p>	<p>Prepare the GA workshops</p> <p>Prepare the research questions deliverable</p>	<p>ETH, ISINNOVA, CICERO</p> <p>ETH, ISINNOVA, All modelling teams</p>
WP3	<p>Following this, Dr Dirk-Jan van de Ven (BC3) informed the consortium that BC3 and E4SMA have sent details to all modelling teams on the technical drafts for MS8, which must be prepared by July. Then, he briefed the partners on the progress made on each of the 6 core models. In this context, Dr Koasidis requested that all modelling teams check the template sent so all models align their work towards the achievement of the relevant milestone.</p>	<p>Check the template sent by BC3 on model documentation</p> <p>Organise a meeting for D4.2 contributors</p>	<p>All modelling teams</p> <p>Imperia</p>
WP4	<p>Then, Dr Maro Malliaroudaki (Imperial) mentioned that D4.1 must be ready by the end of June and that it is on track. She also mentioned that D4.2 must be delivered by the end of July and stated that a meeting with contributing partners will be organised to discuss relevant details. Moreover, on Task 4.3, she informed the consortium that GEMINI, NEMESIS and BC3 teams had a meeting on the required data. On Task 4.6, she mentioned that the UNIBAS and CLEWs teams are having discussions on behavioural aspects in models, while regarding Task 4.7, she informed the consortium that there was a meeting with the OMNIA team that focused on the work done on OpenTEPES. In this context, Dr Marc Vielle</p>		

	(EPFL), Dr Koasidis and Dr van de Ven discussed how to claim linkages between models. Lastly, Dr Koasidis and Dr Malliaroudaki had a discussion on organising a call with all D4.2 contributors, with Dr Malliaroudaki suggesting arranging that mid-May.		
WP5	Following this, Dr Koasidis briefly updated the consortium on WP5 aspects, focusing on the work done on the research questions in cooperation with WP2 partners. He mentioned that two relevant workshops will be hosted during the GA meeting in June. Moreover, he mentioned that in most tasks work is focused on the research questions from the WP2 workshops.	Prepare the research questions workshops for the GA meeting	CICERO, ETH, ISINNOVA
WP6	Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) thanked the teams that completed the pipeline survey and reminded others to do so, noting that the results will feed into D6.6, which he briefly outlined. He also referred to a recent meeting with the CLEWs team on pipeline strategy and visualisation and welcomed similar exchanges with other modelling teams. Dr Koasidis emphasised that D6.6 is due by the end of May and is crucial for MS8. He encouraged all modelling teams to align with the pipeline processes. Dr Xexakis then previewed an upcoming webinar on scenarios assessed by the IPCC which will take place after the GA meeting. It will include keynotes from CICERO and BC3, a discussion with SAB members Dr David McCollum and Prof Jessica Jewell, and participation from external partners. Finally, Dr Koasidis informed the consortium that HOLISTIC is working on updating the I2AM PARIS platform.	Fill in the pipeline survey Prepare D6.6 IPCC processes webinar	All modelling teams HOLISTIC HOLISTIC, CICERO, BC3
WP7	Regarding WP7, Dr Xexakis mentioned that there are no significant updates and then Dr Christina Tigka (ICCS) summarised the progress made on synergies focusing on the interest expressed by the RESCUE research project. She also mentioned that DIAMOND can aim for synergies with other projects as well, encouraging partners to suggest relevant synergies. In a similar context, Dr Koasidis encouraged project partners to examine if their work can be part of webinars hosted by other projects. He mentioned that the ICCS administration team would be glad to facilitate relevant communications. Next, Dr Xexakis asked partners participating in any events organised by modelling communities to get in touch with HOLISTIC partners to coordinate dissemination aspects.		
	Lastly, Dr Koasidis thanked all partners for participating in this meeting.		

4 Scientific Advisory Board meetings

The Scientific Advisory Board is made up of highly esteemed individuals, not belonging to the project's consortium. The SAB's purpose is to provide technical and scientific insight to the project consortium. The members of this board are appointed by the project's General Assembly, comprising one representative from each project partner and the Project Coordinator. The originally proposed synthesis, the Terms of Reference, and the formulation of the SAB have been reported in the project's first milestone report (MS1). DIAMOND's current SAB is comprised of 8 members, ensuring a wide range of experts, as well as gender balance, with its synthesis subject to modification if new challenges/opportunities arise.

4.1 2nd SAB Session: 8 January 2024

The second SAB session was held online during the 1st day of the project's General Assembly. It followed updates from all work packages, enabling the SAB to reflect on the project's progress after its first year. All eight SAB members attended.

Brief Update to SAB

The project consortium presented:

- Key outputs since May 2023 (e.g., Joule paper on Fit for 55 & net-zero pathways; COP28 presentations; engagement in IAM conferences).
- Ongoing efforts to strengthen modelling capacity (e.g., internal workshops, summer schools).
- Updates on stakeholder mapping tools, and the mutual understanding work of WP2.
- Status of model development and upgrades to the I²AM PARIS platform.

SAB Feedback and Discussion Highlights

1. Stakeholder Engagement & EC Guidance
 - EC Direction & Feasibility: the SAB asked whether the EC has guided the project's direction (e.g., on feasibility or sectoral optimisation). The consortium noted no concrete EC direction other than what is prescribed in the Grant, but upcoming review meetings may bring more concrete input.
 - Engagement Approaches: One SAB member shared experience from the CINTRAN project, highlighting the value of practitioner-based exchanges that inform research with real-world challenges.
 - Stakeholder Mapping: the SAB expressed interest in how stakeholder interest/influence was conceptualised. WP2 leaders clarified that mappings are task-specific, helping to define levels of engagement for each actor.
2. Modelling Progress & Strategy
 - Feasibility & Transition Speed: SAB members raised concerns about the feasibility of pathways, especially the speed of change. They suggested going beyond stock-based thresholds (e.g., bioenergy) and incorporating speed constraints and adoption dynamics (e.g., for EVs or heat pumps).
 - Follow-up: The consortium acknowledged the importance of this point and shared that related work is underway in WPs 4–5, including behaviour-informed modelling and risk assessment. A deliverable on stakeholder engagement and further work on feasibility metrics will follow.

- Model Interlinkages & Pipelines: the SAB welcomed progress in model development and asked about shared infrastructure. The consortium discussed individual model pipelines and efforts to embed open science practices (e.g., open data/scripts, validation tools).
 - Regional Focus: the SAB encouraged the project to build on current momentum and expand regional analysis efforts.
 - Community Synergies: SAB members reiterated the value of engagement with sister projects and invited the consortium to ETSAP's biannual meetings and the IEW conference.
3. Transdisciplinary Work
- The ETH team highlighted the mutual understanding process, with seven in-person visits and two reports so far.
 - The SAB appreciated the focus on transdisciplinarity and acknowledged the difficulty of integrating it meaningfully. They encouraged continuing this early engagement of modellers and stakeholders.

Dr. Nikas thanked the SAB for their constructive feedback and noted that more time would be beneficial in future sessions. He invited SAB members to follow up with further questions and offered to share upcoming deliverables for feedback.

4.2 3rd SAB Session: 23 May 2024

This SAB session took place on 23 May 2024, during the 3rd General Assembly (GA) meeting of the DIAMOND project, hosted at EPFL in Lausanne, Switzerland. The GA meeting was held in a hybrid format, allowing remote participation via Zoom. The SAB session was scheduled at the end of the first day of the GA, enabling SAB members to follow the project's latest progress before contributing their insights. Three SAB members attended remotely: Dr. Cecilie Mauritzen, Dr. David McCollum, and Dr. Lukas Hermwille.

The session began with a presentation by project coordinator Dr. Alexandros Nikas (ICCS), who provided an overview of key activities and progress across the project. Highlights included a summary of an SDG-oriented modelling study on EU decarbonisation pathways involving multiple partners, a set of best practices for participatory modelling derived from an internal study, and details on the DIAMOND project's visibility at the EGU conference, where six studies were presented. He also mentioned forthcoming stakeholder engagement activities, including a Requirements Workshop, and introduced the CLEWs-EU single-node model to be used for capacity development. Transparency procedures, ongoing synergies with other projects (including a joint survey on the IPCC scenario submission process alongside the IAM COMPACT project), and updates on collaborations with the WorldTrans and MAIA projects were also discussed.

Further points covered included the status of the I²AM PARIS platform and the conclusion of the first reporting period. Dr. Nikas also updated the SAB on ICCS's involvement in developing net-zero pathways for the city of Athens, following the election of Prof Haris Doukas as mayor.

Key discussion points raised by the SAB included:

- On relevant events: SAB members inquired whether the consortium planned to organise any events at COP29. Dr. Nikas noted that, while no policy outputs were ready due to ongoing model development, the project would remain open to opportunities if they arise. One SAB member suggested that even limited partner participation could be effective. They also proposed that the consortium consider contributing to the UN High-Level Political Forum on Sustainable Development (HLPF) in July 2025, which could serve as a valuable dissemination avenue for the project.

- On modelling and engagement with international processes: SAB members asked whether the consortium is participating in IPCC surveys and whether results from the project's own surveys would be submitted. Dr. Shivika Mittal (CICERO) confirmed that survey data was being collected with this intention. The SAB encouraged sharing these findings with the wider community, noting the IPCC's ambition to make the scenario submission process more dynamic and iterative. They also informed the consortium about an upcoming IPCC workshop on scenarios in Bangkok.
- On model robustness and policy relevance: the SAB advised the consortium to remain attentive to the evolving policy landscape, especially in the light of the upcoming EU elections, which could affect the direction of policy outreach. A member also encouraged modelling extreme or abrupt scenarios, such as a trade conflict between major economies, to test the resilience of the project's tools. Dr. Nikas noted that colleagues at Imperial are already exploring such disruptions and that WP5 is focused on assessing model robustness under extreme conditions.
- On participatory modelling and stakeholder validation: The SAB emphasised the importance of validating models with stakeholders and asked how the success of the project's participatory framework would be evaluated. Dr. Bianca Vienni-Baptista (ETH) responded that a dedicated task in the next phase of the project will focus on implementing and testing the participatory framework.
- On performance tracking and project KPIs: an SAB member stressed the importance of assessing the project's progress against its KPIs. Dr. Nikas replied that, while KPI parameters (e.g., conference attendance) are tracked, there is no consolidated documentation yet. He acknowledged the value of raising awareness among partners, nonetheless.

The session concluded with Dr. Nikas thanking the SAB members for their participation and insightful contributions.

4.3 4th SAB Session: 29 January 2025

This SAB session was organised in the context of the 4th General Assembly (GA) meeting of DIAMOND, held online via Microsoft Teams on 29 January 2025. The session took place after the lunch break and lasted one hour, enabling the (four) attending SAB members to be informed of the latest project developments.

The session was opened by Dr. Alexandros Nikas (ICCS), who welcomed the SAB members and announced that the next GA meeting would take place physically in Oslo, Norway, encouraging efforts to facilitate in-person participation. He then gave a brief overview of the project's progress, beginning with key points from the Commission's monitoring of the 1st Reporting Period. All submitted deliverables had been approved, with one main recommendation being to enhance the publication strategy, particularly as several publications are expected after the project's completion. Dr. Nikas presented highlights of the project's outputs since May, including submitted publications, scientific outreach, and networking activities in 2024. He provided an overview of stakeholder engagement efforts, summarising completed workshops and noting that more are planned for 2025, including the upcoming 2nd Foresight workshop. He also outlined progress on model development and linkages, showcased the DIAMOND scenario space, and explained how the models are expected to be used. Finally, he summarised the Open Science Protocol and gave a brief overview of the project's next steps for the following six months.

Key discussion points raised by the SAB included:

- On stakeholder engagement and impact:
 - The SAB stressed the importance of maximising the visibility and impact of stakeholder engagement

- activities, including through the publication of reports.
- SAB and project partners suggested creating a dedicated space on the project website to showcase transdisciplinary and participatory activities, a recommendation positively received by the consortium.
 - There was encouragement to clarify the project's contribution and unique value proposition (USP/UVP), particularly by explicitly outlining what DIAMOND is doing that others are not.
 - On scenarios and model development:
 - One SAB member highlighted the lack of dystopian or disruptive scenarios in many modelling efforts, suggesting DIAMOND could help fill this gap. Examples mentioned include low energy demand scenarios or reduced trade scenarios, and how such futures might affect political systems or global dynamics. Dr. Peters and Dr. Mittal noted that some WP5 tasks already explore disruptive futures, and that this direction could be pursued further.
 - Another SAB member referred to broader scenario debates in the community (e.g., SSPs, DERPs) and pointed to venues such as the Scenarios Forum and a planned special issue in the Futures journal. A suggestion was made to organise a dedicated session on scenarios (possibly with SAB involvement), either internally or through community fora. The SAB acknowledged the constraints of the project scope but encouraged DIAMOND partners to stay engaged with scenario developments, possibly contributing to post-project initiatives and proposals.
 - On project visibility and continuity:
 - The SAB raised the idea of framing project achievements for broader communication, suggesting simple messages such as "we did this, and this fills a gap".
 - The SAB proposed a strategic meeting to explore potential future directions for the consortium, including follow-up projects, after the updated Model Development Strategy is delivered.
 - The consortium welcomed this and expressed willingness to host a dedicated SAB session or meeting to support future planning and deepen engagement.